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Manuscript Draft

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Title: Steady-state NH₃-SCR global model and kinetic parameter estimation for NO_x removal in diesel engine exhaust aftertreatment with Cu over chabazite-type zeolite

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Abstract: A steady-state global kinetic model for the NO_x NH₃-SCR reaction system, including NH₃ oxidation, NO oxidation, standard SCR reaction, fast SCR reaction, NO₂ SCR reaction, and N₂O formation and decomposition is proposed, based on the Eley-Rideal formalism in which only ammonia is adsorbed and NO reacts directly from the gas phase. The experimental runs were designed under operational conditions simulating NO, NH₃, NO₂ feed stream composition near to the real application for NO_x removal from diesel engine automobile exhaust aftertreatment. An initial set of 62 experiments, with only NO₂ and NH₃ in the feed stream allows a preliminary estimation of some kinetic parameters. Additional extensive experimentation up to 176 runs under a wide range of feed stream composition, temperature and space time was carried out. The experimental outlet NO, NH₃, NO₂ and N₂O concentrations are analyzed for kinetic parameter estimation of seven reactions included in the proposed global NO_x NH₃-SCR system, resulting in activation energy values for standard SCR reaction, fast SCR reaction and NO₂ SCR reaction of 91.5, 42.0, and 118 kJ mol⁻¹, respectively. The proposed model resulted of high statistical significance deduced from the analysis of variance, with a determination coefficient of 0.952, and excellent F-test for a probability superior to 99%.

AUTHORS' ANSWERS TO REVIEWERS (CATTOD-D-17-00043)

Dear Editor,

Thank you very much for your letter including the suggestions by Reviewers to improve the quality of our manuscript. Following are listed the comments of reviewers with our answers and corrections inserted in red color. Also you can find a marked version of the new manuscript, in which we have indicated in blue color amendments made, and in red color removal of text, according to Reviewers' suggestions.

REVIEWER #1.

The paper presents the development of a steady-state global kinetic model for the NOx NH₃-SCR reactions for a Cu-chabazite catalyst.

Before publication, the authors have to address the following points:

1. Reaction nomenclature is not always consistent throughout the paper. The slow SCR is reaction between NO and ammonia only, while the NO₂ SCR is the reaction between NO₂ and ammonia only.

Yes, this was true. The nomenclature has been revised and now reactions between NO₂ and NH₃ are named as NO₂ SCR throughout the paper. Also, each reaction in the network has been specifically referred to.

2. SCR reaction network: they have to justify their choices, and add references for the different reactions they introduce.

We have modified the way in which different reactions are introduced in the chosen SCR reaction network. In the actual Section 2, The SCR reaction, previous equation (9) has been eliminated (page 6, lines 158 to 163), which now is introduced as equation (14) according to our own experimental observations; this has been explained in a new paragraph (pages 10-11, lines 280 to 294).

Reaction (9): can the authors provide references for this reaction? Do they have experimental evidence for that?

As said in the previous answer we introduce previous equation 9 (now equation 14) as a consequence of our own experimental observations. However, also 2 new references (refs. 68 and 69) by other authors have been introduced reporting the existence of this reaction (page 11, lines 290 to 294).

Also, I notice that they do not include formation of N₂O from standard SCR and ammonia oxidation. Again, they should justify their choice.

Standard SCR reaction is universally accepted as described by equation (1), NO₂ reacts with NH₃ in the presence of oxygen to give N₂. This does not mean that other

subproducts as N_2O are not formed as a consequence of occurring parallel reactions, equations (5) to (8), already included in the global proposed reaction network.

They also state that N_2O decomposes to N_2 and O_2 . This is quite known for Fe zeolite catalysts, but not well documented for Cu-chabazite.

As it is explained in the text, the higher N_2O concentration values when N_2O decomposition was not considered allowed us to include this reaction. To document this fact with previous evidences in literature, two references (refs. 49 to 51) where N_2O decomposition occurs over different Me/zeolite, including Cu/zeolite, have been included in new version (page 7, lines 165 to 167).

3. Experimental: did the authors check the mass balances? Typical concentrations of reactants should be specified. Was water present in the feed mixture?

Closing of the mass balance for different N-species was checked as Ar was used as inert gas to balance. NO, NO_2 , N_2O and NH_3 were analyzed by MKS FTIR, and N_2 by MKS MS, as explained in the paper. The N-compounds mass balances in experimental data closed under 5%-error. On the other hand, all experiments were achieved in the absence of water, and products analysis was realized after water removal at the reactor exit (page 9, lines 227 to 228).

Kinetic model: I don't see why they introduce and comment only some of the reactions included in the complete scheme.

In the new version, the kinetic model is introduced once all reactions have been explained and their inclusion in the complete scheme justified. Previous introduction has been removed (page 9, lines 236 to 246), and new explanation has been included in the new version, at the end of the Section 3.3. Kinetic model (page 10-11, lines 280 to 302).

4. Kinetic parameters: the provided values should be commented, and compared with others already reported in the literature.

The obtained activation energy obtained for the standard SCR reaction, the fast SCR reaction and the NO_2 SCR reaction in the proposed kinetic model, have been compared and discussed with those found in previously reported models in literature by other authors, namely Metkar et al. [10] and Olsson et al. [36]. (Page 15, lines 431 to 438).

5. The description of the results seems quite fast...

We have revised results throughout the paper, and have introduced deeper discussion in some of the passages, as explained in our answers to previous questions and suggestion of this Reviewer.

REVIEWER #2:

This manuscript contains useful experimental data and a global kinetic model of the NH_3 -NSR reactions in the 200-350 °C range. The experiments were conducted using catalyst particles of particles of 300-500 micron diameter. It would be very useful to report some experiments that prove that internal diffusion and external mass transfer had a negligible impact on all the reactions in this temperature range. This could be done by reporting the computed values of the effectiveness factors at 350 for all these reactions. The authors must be aware of this important need as they mention in the closing conclusions section that there is a need to study in the future the impact of diffusion in washcoated monolith catalysts. As they have determined the kinetic rate constant, this can be done by mathematical modelling. Moreover, it would be useful to use such a model to estimate at what temperature above 350 °C diffusion is expected to affect the performance.

We agree with the Reviewer of the big importance of this figure in the analysis. This had not been included in the previous version just because of space limitation. According to the suggestion, a new section 4.3. Influence of the mass transfer inside the catalyst particle, has been added (page 17-18, lines 499 to 529).

I would suggest to add an explanation of the rather large experimental scatter of the fast SCR data in Fig. 5 and the rather large scatter of the calculated vs. the experimental N_2O data in Fig. 6.

We have tried to extend explanation of the rather large experimental scatter of some data, although unfortunately this only could be avoided by inclusion of new reaction in the global scheme. Nevertheless, the model is able to explain a large percentage of the variation sources with a determination coefficient of $r^2=0.952$ and a very high statistical signification.

The manuscript requires text editing in several locations. For example, the abstract contains "The experiments were design", "feedstream", The model "resulted of high determination coefficients".

In order to correct the text editing mistakes, the manuscript has been fully revised and edited.

Invitation Letter

Guest Editors Name: Juan Bussi, Jorge Castiglioni and Carlos Apesteguía
Special Issue Title: XXV CICAT

Dear participant in XXV CICAT,

It is our pleasure to invite you to submit a manuscript from your presentation at the XXV Iberoamerican Congress on Catalysis for a special issue of Catalysis Today dedicated to XXV CICAT.

All manuscripts will be peer reviewed and, to be published, they must meet all the standards of this journal. In the case you are willing to submit a manuscript, please follow the instructions attached to this message.

All communications on manuscripts submission and reviews will be managed within the Elsevier Editorial System (EES). Please note that deadline for manuscript submission is **December 15, 2016**

Yours sincerely

Juan Bussi, Jorge Castiglioni and Carlos Apesteguía
Guest Editors of the Special Issue XXV CICAT

Highlights

- A global kinetic model for NO_x NH₃-SCR reaction network is proposed.
- The model is based on nonlinear regression of 176 experiments, varying feedstream composition, space time and temperature.
- Optimal kinetic parameters for standard, fast and slow SCR reactions are estimated.
- The proposed model describes experimental data with high statistical significance.

The proposed NO_x-NH₃-SCR reaction network, based on nonlinear regression of 176 reaction experiments

- I. $\text{NH}_3 + 3/4 \text{O}_2 \rightarrow 1/2 \text{N}_2 + 3/2 \text{H}_2\text{O}$
- II. $\text{NO} + 1/2 \text{O}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{NO}_2$
- III. $\text{NH}_3 + \text{NO} + 1/4 \text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{N}_2 + 3/2 \text{H}_2\text{O}$
- IV. $2 \text{NH}_3 + \text{NO} + \text{NO}_2 \rightarrow 2 \text{N}_2 + 3 \text{H}_2\text{O}$
- V. $4 \text{NH}_3 + 3 \text{NO}_2 \rightarrow 7/2 \text{N}_2 + 6 \text{H}_2\text{O}$
- VI. $3 \text{NH}_3 + 4 \text{NO}_2 \rightarrow 7/2 \text{N}_2\text{O} + 9/2 \text{H}_2\text{O}$
- VII. $2 \text{N}_2\text{O} \rightarrow 2 \text{N}_2 + \text{O}_2$

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**Steady-state NH₃-SCR global model and kinetic
parameter estimation for NO_x removal in diesel
engine exhaust aftertreatment with Cu/chabazite**

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Keywords:

NH₃-SCR, NO_x removal, kinetic model, parameter estimation, Cu/CHA, chabazite

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23 **Abstract**

24 A steady-state global kinetic model for the NO_x NH_3 -SCR reaction system, including NH_3
25 oxidation, NO oxidation, standard SCR reaction, fast SCR reaction, NO_2 SCR reaction,
26 and N_2O formation and decomposition is proposed, based on the Eley-Rideal formalism
27 in which only ammonia is adsorbed and NO reacts directly from the gas phase. The
28 experimental runs were designed under operational conditions simulating NO, NH_3 , NO_2
29 feed stream composition near to the real application for NO_x removal from diesel engine
30 automobile exhaust aftertreatment. An initial set of 62 experiments, with only NO_2 and
31 NH_3 in the feed stream allows a preliminary estimation of some kinetic parameters.
32 Additional extensive experimentation up to 176 runs under a wide range of feed stream
33 composition, temperature and space time was carried out. The experimental outlet NO,
34 NH_3 , NO_2 and N_2O concentrations are analyzed for kinetic parameter estimation of seven
35 reactions included in the proposed global NO_x NH_3 -SCR system, resulting in activation
36 energy values for standard SCR reaction, fast SCR reaction and NO_2 SCR reaction of
37 91.5, 42.0, and 118 kJ mol^{-1} , respectively. The proposed model resulted of high statistical
38 significance deduced from the analysis of variance, with a determination coefficient of
39 0.952, and excellent F-test for a probability superior to 99%.

40 1. Introduction

41 The selective catalytic reduction (SCR) by NH₃ has been considered for many years the
42 most efficient control technology to remove noxious environmental NO_x emissions from
43 chemical plants and stationary power sources, mainly achieved on Mo- or W-promoted
44 V₂O₅-TiO₂ catalysts [1-4]. In 2005, the SCR technology was brought to the market for
45 heavy duty vehicles already, based on the use of similar formulation on honeycomb
46 monolith catalysts [5]. However, the low stability of vanadia at high temperature and
47 more and more stricter NO_x emission regulations for both heavy and low duty vehicles,
48 which requires higher activity at low temperature, have motivated the introduction of
49 zeolite-based catalysts promoted by transition metals, as iron [6-8] and copper [9-15].

50 The most extensive studies have been carried out on Cu²⁺ ion-exchanged ZSM-5
51 (Cu/ZSM-5) zeolites, first shown to achieve high NO decomposition rates and NO_x SCR
52 activity [6, 13, 16]. Later, Cu²⁺ ion-exchanged beta zeolite (Cu/beta) was shown to have
53 excellent NO_x NH₃-SCR activity with better hydrothermal stability than ZSM-5 catalysts
54 [12, 17]. Yet, none of these zeolites show durability sufficient for the automotive industry.
55 In the year 2010, Cu²⁺-exchanged molecular sieves with chabazite (CHA) structures, for
56 example, Cu/SSZ-13 and Cu/SAPO-34, have been discovered to show apparently much
57 improved activity, selectivity, and durability for exhausts aftertreatment in diesel and lean
58 burn engines [18-21].

59 We and other researchers compared SCR activities and hydrothermal stabilities of
60 Cu/CHA with other Cu²⁺ ion-exchanged zeolites, especially Cu/ZSM-5 and Cu/beta [14,
61 18, 19]. Indeed, Cu/CHA shows comparable or even higher activity, higher N₂ selectivity
62 and most impressively, much higher hydrothermal stability even under harsh conditions;
63 for example, extended hydrothermal treatments at 1073 K.

64 The standard SCR reaction between NO and NH₃ occurs in the presence of oxygen:

66 Many studies have shown that the NO_x reduction activity increases if NO and NO₂ are
67 fed in equimolecular amount [22]. The reaction between equimolecular amounts of NO
68 and NO₂ with NH₃ is known as the fast SCR reaction:

70 The third important reaction in this chemistry is **NO₂ SCR** reaction:

72 This reaction is important when the feed NO_x comprises mostly NO_2 . While the presence
73 of NO_2 accelerates the NO_x reduction rate on various catalysts [22], its presence
74 complicates the overall NH_3 -SCR reaction chemistry [23]. NO_2 has been proposed as the
75 key species for the SCR of NO_x with NH_3 on various zeolite catalysts, and the oxidation
76 of NO to NO_2 is the likely rate-limiting step [24]. Stevenson et al. [25] and Wallin et al.
77 [26] argued that oxidation of NO is the rate determining step in the reduction of NO by
78 NH_3 on H-ZSM-5. Many other studies have focused on the mechanistic issues for the
79 SCR chemistry. Komatsu et al. [27] suggested a mechanism for the standard SCR reaction
80 on Cu-zeolite catalysts that involves the formation of a bridging NO_3 molecule which
81 further reacts with NO to form NO_2 . The NO_2 then reacts with NH_3 to produce N_2 and
82 H_2O . Other studies presented a mechanistic model in which the preferred path for NO_x
83 reduction with ammonia occurs via ammonium nitrite, which decomposes to N_2 and H_2O
84 [28]; and others have suggested that the reduction of NO and NO_2 by NH_3 involves the
85 formation of HNO_2 and HNO_3 [29, 30]. We tried to understand the role of the different
86 copper species on the activity of Cu/H-ZSM-5 and Cu/H-BETA catalysts in the NH_3 -SCR
87 process for NO_x removal in a wide temperature range (140–500 °C) [12], suggesting that
88 the nature of the copper species affects the SCR behavior of catalyst. CuO clusters
89 promote NO reduction at low temperature whereas isolated Cu(II) ions maintain high
90 NO_x conversion at high temperatures. In addition, catalysts with low CuO content exhibit
91 higher N_2 selectivity, since CuO promotes the formation of N_2O and NO_2 . Unlike
92 hydrothermally treated Cu/ZSM-5 and Cu/BETA catalysts, minor changes in the copper
93 sites were observed on Cu/SSZ-13, which was consistent with the minor changes in the
94 SCR activity of the Cu/SSZ-13 catalyst after the hydrothermal treatment process [14, 31,
95 32].

96 In spite of a host of experimental studies focused on mechanistic issues and reaction
97 pathways, a much smaller number of studies have focused on the kinetic modeling of
98 NH_3 -SCR reactions. Several studies presented steady-state global kinetic models for the
99 standard SCR for vanadia-based catalysts [1, 33, 34], Cu/ZSM-5 [35, 36] and Cu/faujasite
100 [37]. Nova et al. [38, 39] developed a detailed transient kinetic model, while Chatterjee
101 et al. [40-42] developed a global kinetic model for both vanadia- and Fe/zeolite catalysts.
102 Their model describes well the transient and steady-state NO_x conversion and the effect
103 of feed NO/NO_2 ratio on the NH_3 -SCR chemistry. Olsson and coworkers developed both

104 global and detailed kinetic models for NH₃-SCR reactions on Fe/ZSM-5 and Cu/ZSM-5
105 catalysts [36, 43-46]. Their kinetic models account for transient effects for various feed
106 concentrations of NO₂. To our knowledge, there is no kinetic model available for the
107 recently commercialized small pore Cu/CHA catalyst, with the exception of the 1+1
108 dimensional reactor model presented by Metkar et al. [10], which includes external
109 transport and washcoat diffusion processes. According to our previous work [14],
110 Cu/CHA achieves superior performance in the NO NH₃-SCR reaction, with practically
111 100% NO conversion from 220 to 380 °C. At higher temperatures, the presence of water
112 in the feed stream may even improve NO conversion at higher temperatures due to the
113 inhibition of ammonia oxidation, whereas small differences are observed in the low-
114 medium temperature range. In contrast, Cu/ZSM-5 and Cu/BETA suffer from significant
115 destruction of surface area, acidity and surface reducibility with hydrothermal aging,
116 causing notable decrease in their catalytic performance.

117 The main objective of the current study is to develop a global kinetic model that predicts
118 the main features of various NO/NO₂/NH₃ reactions occurring during NH₃-SCR on
119 Cu/chabazite (CHA). The kinetic model considers ammonia adsorption and desorption,
120 NH₃ oxidation, NO oxidation, standard SCR, fast SCR, NO₂ SCR, N₂O formation and
121 N₂O decomposition. The model is deduced from an extended set of experiments carried
122 out under conditions simulating the automobile application, but with powdered catalyst
123 in the absence of diffusional control, and with validation under an extended temperature
124 range, i.e. 225-350 °C. The model is intended to be as simple as possible to be
125 implemented in mathematical modeling of washcoated honeycombs under one- or
126 multidimensional reactor models, which allow predicting improvements of the catalyst
127 performance in terms of the washcoat characteristics as well as the temperature
128 performance windows.

129

130 **2. The SCR reaction network**

131 A completed, detailed description of the NH₃-SCR technology can be found in the recent
132 book of Nova and Tronconi [47], including mechanistic aspects and reaction kinetics for
133 Cu/zeolite catalysts [48]. Both fundamental detailed kinetic models as well as more
134 globalized models have been discussed in literature [36, 39, 41, 44].

135 In addition to the three main reactions already mentioned as standard SCR (reaction 1),
 136 fast SCR (reaction 2), and **NO₂ SCR** (reaction 3) to produce nitrogen, also a number of
 137 secondary reactions occurs leading to undesired consumption of NH₃ or generation of
 138 subproducts as N₂O, NH₄NO₃ and HNO₃. The oxidation of NH₃ is an important lateral
 139 reaction which occurs mainly at temperature higher than 350 °C, not desirable as it
 140 decreases availability of NH₃ needed for reactions (1)-(3),

142 On the other hand, the oxidation of NO to NO₂ reaches equilibrium conditions at
 143 temperature 150-200 °C that are decreasing with increasing temperature (exothermic
 144 reaction):

146 Reaction (5) is desirable as NO₂ is reduced with NH₃ more efficiently than NO (fast vs.
 147 standard SCR reactions); on the contrary, the existence of NO₂ makes more complex the
 148 reaction network.

149 N₂O is an unwanted by-product during the SCR process over copper zeolites that
 150 increases with the NO₂ content. The mechanism for the N₂O production is suggested to
 151 be from the decomposition of ammonium nitrate above 200 °C, the later formed by
 152 reaction of ammonia with NO₂:

155 In fact, combination of reactions (6) and (7) yields to another **NO₂ SCR** reaction
 156 producing undesirable N₂O to be considered in the SCR system.

158 ~~In addition, NH₃ and NO₂ can react with other stoichiometry to form N₂O, which can be~~
 159 ~~eonform uneven consumption of reactants (equation 9), opposite to that of slow NO₂-SCR~~
 160 ~~reaction (equation 3).~~

162 ~~The extent of reaction (3), (8) and (9) under different experimental conditions achieves~~
 163 ~~N₂/N₂O selectivity of reaction network.~~

164 On the other hand, N₂O decomposes into N₂ and O₂ at higher temperatures (reaction 9),
165 as already reported by several authors [49-51] on MFI, BEA and FAU zeolites doped with
166 Fe, Cu and Co. The samples activity depends on the introduced transition metal and the
167 following order of their activation effect: Cu > Co > Fe was observed [52].

169

170 3. Experimental

171 3.1. Catalyst preparation

172 First, N,N,N-trimethyl-1-adamantammonium (TMAda) was prepared for its use as
173 organic structure directing agent (OSDA) in the synthesis of chabazite. For this purpose,
174 29.6 g of 1-Adamantamine (Sigma-Aldrich) and 64 g of potassium carbonate (Sigma-
175 Aldrich) were mixed with 320 ml of chloroform. Then, 75 g of methyl iodide was added
176 dropwise while the reaction was stirred in an ice bath. The reaction was maintained for 5
177 days under agitation at room temperature. The mixture was filtered and washed with
178 diethyl ether, and the resultant solid further extracted with chloroform. The final product
179 was N,N,N-trimethyl-1-adamantammonium iodide. This iodide salt was anion exchanged
180 using an ion exchange resin, and finally, an aqueous solution of the hydroxide form of
181 TMAda was achieved (7.6% wt).

182 Chabazite zeolite was prepared following the former synthesis description reported by
183 Zones [53]. In this sense, 1.45 g of sodium hydroxide (Sigma-Aldrich, 98%) was
184 dissolved in 99.9 g of an aqueous solution of N,N,N-trimethyl-1-adamantammonium
185 hydroxide (7.6% wt), and the mixture was maintained under stirring for 15 minutes. Then,
186 1.0 g of aluminum hydroxide (66% wt, Sigma-Aldrich) and 10.9 g of fumed silica (aerosil)
187 were introduced in the synthesis mixture, and maintained under stirring the required time
188 to evaporate the solvent until the desired gel concentration. The final gel composition was
189 SiO₂:0.037 Al₂O₃:0.20 TMAda:0.20 NaOH:18.3 H₂O. The gel was transferred to an
190 autoclave with a Teflon liner, and heated at 150 °C for 5 days under dynamic conditions.
191 The sample after hydrothermal crystallization was filtered and washed with abundant
192 distilled water, and finally dried at 100 °C. Finally, CHA zeolite was calcined at 580 °C
193 for 4 h.

194 Ion exchange (IE) was the method used for preparing the Cu-exchanged CHA zeolite.
195 The sample was first washed with a 0.04 M aqueous solution of NaNO₃ (~150 ml/g of

196 zeolite). Then, the Cu IE was conducted using an aqueous solution of $\text{Cu}(\text{CH}_3\text{CO}_2)_2$
197 containing the required amount of Cu. The liquid to solid ratio was fixed at 100 ml/g of
198 zeolite, and the resultant mixture was maintained under stirring overnight at room
199 temperature. Finally, the sample was filtered and washed with distilled water, and
200 calcined at 550 °C for 4 h. The prepared powdered catalysts were then pelletized, crushed
201 and sieved to 0.3-0.5 mm. Previous experiments carried out with different particle size
202 catalysts revealed that mass transfer limitations could be considered negligible, so that
203 internal diffusion in the catalyst particle was not the rate-controlling step in the kinetic
204 mechanism for this particle size of 0.3-0.5 mm.

205 The actual chemical compositions of the powdered Cu/CHA zeolite resulted in Si/Al ratio
206 of 10.6 and a loading of 3.9% Cu, which was used for kinetic experiments.

207 *3.2. Reaction and product analysis setup*

208 The experiments were performed in a vertical downflow stainless steel reactor. The
209 reactor tube, 13 mm inner diameter, was placed into a 3-zone tube furnace. In order to
210 obtain kinetic data for extended range of space times, experiments were performed with
211 different catalyst weight and total feed flow, varying from 0.05 to 0.5 g and 1.0 to 3.3 l
212 $C_{\text{NO}} = C_{\text{NO}_2} = C_{\text{NH}_3} = 300 \text{ ppm}$ and $C_{\text{O}_2} = 20\%$, min^{-1} , respectively. Typical reactant
213 concentrations used for experimental runs were but also these values were extensively
214 varied when the effect of every reactant were observed (see Supplementary Material, later
215 for every experimental data set). The presence of water in feed stream was not included
216 in the kinetic analysis. The reactor was filled with the corresponding weight of catalyst
217 until a volume of 2 ml, being diluted with inert quartz ground at the same particle size
218 than catalyst (300-500 μm). All the lines of the installation were heated at 200 °C avoiding
219 NH_4NO_3 formation which decomposed at this temperature into N_2O and H_2O by reaction
220 (7). This fact has been verified by good closing of N-compounds balance in an initial set
221 of experiments.

222 Gases (NO , NO_2 , NH_3 , O_2 and Ar) were fed via mass flow controllers. Argon was used
223 as inert gas, allowing analysis of nitrogen at the exit gas. The outlet gas concentrations
224 were continuously measured using a MKS MultiGas 2030 FT-IR analyzer followed by a
225 MKS Cirrus quadrupole MS on line. NO , NO_2 , NH_3 , N_2O and H_2O were quantitatively
226 monitored by the FT-IR analyzer, whereas H_2 , N_2 and O_2 were monitored by the MS

227 analyzer. The N-compounds mass balances in experimental data closed under 5%-error
228 for all experimental runs.

229 3.3. Kinetic model

230 Taking into account the SCR reaction network above described, we chose initially the
231 reaction mechanism described by the following reactions: i) ammonia oxidation (reaction
232 4), ii) NO oxidation (reaction 5), iii) standard SCR (reaction 1), iv) fast SCR (reaction 2),
233 v) **NO₂ SCR** (reaction 3), vi) N₂O formation (reaction 8), and vii) N₂O decomposition
234 (reaction 9). As already mentioned, ammonium nitrates are not considered in the scheme
235 as they decomposed directly into N₂O and H₂O at 200 °C, at which temperature all lines
236 are heated in the experimental setup. ~~This reaction network is expressed in the first
237 column of Table 1.~~

238 ~~TABLE 1~~

~~239 In the case of N₂O formation, either reaction (8) or reaction (9) can be considered for the
240 network. The analysis of the first set of experiments (see Table S1 in supplementary
241 material) in which NH₃/NO₂ equimolecular stream is fed, indicates more consumption of
242 NO₂ than NH₃ (outlet NH₃ concentration higher than outlet NO₂ concentration). This
243 condition indicates that reaction (9) is needed in the reaction network inevitably. On the
244 other hand, reaction (8) is not necessary to be considered as it can be deduced as a
245 combination of equations (3) and (9), already included in Table 1 as reactions V and VI,
246 respectively.~~

247 A good description of the ammonia storage and desorption is critical in order to describe
248 transient features of the SCR system. Detailed kinetic models for ammonia adsorption
249 and desorption usually use a Temkin type of kinetics that considers adsorbate-adsorbate
250 interactions [44, 54] in line with previous proposals for V-based catalysts [55, 56]. In the
251 case of global models, Langmuir-Hinshelwood [35, 57] or Eley-Rideal [25, 58] models
252 are usually assumed for the kinetic equations, considering that both NH₃ and NO are
253 adsorbed on the catalyst active sites (Langmuir-Hinshelwood) or that NH₃ is adsorbed
254 but NO reacts directly from the gas phase (Eley-Rideal). We have initially postulated that
255 the kinetics obeys an Eley-Rideal formalism between gaseous NO and adsorbed NH₃, or
256 better a Langmuir-Hinshelwood formalism with weakly adsorbed NO species [43, 59-
257 62]. If ammonia adsorption and desorption are in equilibrium,

259 the fraction of sites adsorbed of ammonia will be related to ammonia concentration by a
 260 Langmuir-Hinshelwood expression:

$$261 \quad \theta_{\text{NH}_3\text{-S1}} = \frac{K_{\text{NH}_3} C_{\text{NH}_3}}{1 + K_{\text{NH}_3} C_{\text{NH}_3}} \quad (11)$$

263 where K_{NH_3} is the ammonia adsorption equilibrium constant. With this assumption we
 264 can describe the SCR kinetic equations for steps I, III, IV, V and VI, as listed in Table 1.

265 The NO to NO₂ oxidation reaction (step II in Table 1) has been considered in equilibrium
 266 in the gas phase, without the participation of any adsorbed species, being described by

$$267 \quad r_{\text{II}} = k_{\text{II}} (C_{\text{NO}} C_{\text{O}_2}^{0.5} - C_{\text{NO}_2} / K_{\text{NO}}^{\text{eq.}}) \quad (12)$$

268 The equilibrium constant has been determined thermodynamically from the formation
 269 heats of the components NO and NO₂, resulting in

$$270 \quad K_{\text{NO}}^{\text{eq.}} = 8.31 \times 10^{-4} \exp\left(\frac{5728}{RT}\right) \quad (13)$$

272 For the N₂O decomposition (reaction VII in Table 1), different mechanisms have been
 273 proposed in the literature [50, 63-67] in which N₂O reacts from the gas phase and
 274 generating N₂ in the gas phase and O ad-atom on the catalyst. Then two adjacent O ad-
 275 atoms conform O₂ in the gas phase. More recent microkinetic schemes based in DFT [67],
 276 have suggested a more complex scheme for the formation of O₂, with a higher number of
 277 elementary steps; and transient studies in TAP reactor [66] indicates that the reaction
 278 mechanism is not influenced neither for the metal species in the catalyst nor for its
 279 incorporation method.

280 An initial set of experiments was realized with NO₂ and NH₃, but neither NO nor O₂ in
 281 feed stream (Table S1, supplementary material), as then only reactions (3), (8) and (9) are
 282 involved in the reduced reaction network. In fact, this experimental data set will be firstly
 283 kinetically analyzed later in the paper. However, qualitative observation of data reveals
 284 more disappearance of NO₂ than NH₃, opposite to that expected when considering
 285 reactions (3) and (8), which predict more consumption of NH₃ than NO₂ and even
 286 consumption, respectively. With the aim of approaching the model to experimental
 287 observation, we considered less NO₂ reduction by reaction (8), remaining unreduced N₂O
 288 as product,

290 This reaction has already been described in literature at temperatures below 350 °C for
 291 NH₃-SCR on zeolite-based catalysts [68, 69]. Then, reaction (8) can be removed from the
 292 kinetic scheme, as it is equivalent to linear combination of reactions (3) and (14),
 293 providing stoichiometry as experimentally observed. In fact, experimental data (Table
 294 S1) fit with high significance the proposed, reduced kinetic model (see later).

295 Additionally, a best fitting of the experimental data sets in Table S1 (experiments 1 to 62,
 296 supplementary material), demanded us to include in the kinetic equation corresponding
 297 to N₂O decomposition (reaction 9) not only C_{N_2O} but also C_{NO_2} , resulting in
 298 the following expression:

$$299 \quad r_{VII} = k_{VII} C_{N_2O} C_{NO_2} \quad (15)$$

300 In summary, the reaction network finally proposed for establishing the global kinetic
 301 model and parameter estimation is composed of seven reactions as described in Table 1.

302 **TABLE 1**

303 *3.4. The ordinary differential equation system*

304 Considering isothermal fixed bed reactor, with ideal plug flow model, the differential
 305 material balance for the species i is expressed as

$$306 \quad \frac{dC_i}{d(W/Q)} = \sum_{j=I}^{VII} n_{i,j} r_j \quad (16)$$

307 where r_j represents the rate of reaction I to VII (Table 1) and $n_{i,j}$ are the stoichiometric
 308 coefficients of component i in reaction j , considered positive for formed species and
 309 negative for disappeared species. Thus, the reaction rate for each component in the
 310 medium is evaluated as:

$$311 \quad \frac{dC_{NH_3}}{d[W/Q]} = -r_I - r_{III} - 2r_{IV} - 4r_V - 3r_{VI} \quad (17)$$

$$313 \quad \frac{dC_{NO}}{d[W/Q]} = -r_{II} - r_{III} - r_{IV} \quad (18)$$

$$315 \quad \frac{dC_{NO_2}}{d[W/Q]} = r_{II} - r_{IV} - 3r_V - 4r_{VI} \quad (19)$$

$$317 \quad \frac{dC_{N_2O}}{d[W/Q]} = \frac{7}{2} r_{VI} - 2r_{VII} \quad (20)$$

319

320 **4. Results and discussion**

321 *4.1. Design of experiments*

322 As above mentioned, first step for planning kinetic experiments was to consider the
323 possibility of monitoring a limited number of components by choosing a subset of
324 reactions of those included in the whole reaction network in Table 1. This reduced subset
325 consisted of reactions V, VI and VII corresponding to the **NO₂ SCR** reaction and
326 formation-decomposition of N₂O, in the absence of NO and oxygen in the feed stream.
327 In this sense, 62 experiments were designed at the conditions established in sets 1 and 2
328 of Table 2, feeding NO₂ and NH₃ with initial concentration ratios $C_{\text{NO}_2}^0 / C_{\text{NH}_3}^0 =$
329 300/300 ppm (29 experiments) and $C_{\text{NO}_2}^0 / C_{\text{NH}_3}^0 = 300/400$ ppm (33 experiments), and
330 temperature of 225, 250, 300 and 350 °C. The composition of the outlet stream for each
331 experiment is detailed in Tables S1 and S2 (supplementary material), respectively.

332

TABLE 2

333 It was not possible to propose another subset of reactions whose analysis could be done
334 independently, since the introduction of NO in the feed stream starts up all the reactions
335 in the whole network (reactions I to VII) and all products formed in the environment.
336 Then, 36 experiments (set 3, from 63 to 98) were performed for the standard SCR reaction
337 (NO+NH₃+O₂), with $C_{\text{NO}}^0 / C_{\text{NH}_3}^0 = 300/800$ and $800/300$ ppm, $C_{\text{O}_2}^0 = 6\%$, and $T =$
338 225, 250, 300 and 350 °C; 22 experiments (set 4, from 99 to 120) for ammonia oxidation,
339 with $C_{\text{NH}_3}^0 = 300\text{-}5000$ ppm and $C_{\text{O}_2}^0 = 6\%$, $T = 225, 250$ and 300 °C; 13
340 experiments (set 5, from 121 to 133) for NO oxidation, with $C_{\text{NO}}^0 = 200, 330$ ppm
341 and $C_{\text{O}_2}^0 = 6\%$ between 150 and 500 °C; and 43 experiments (set 6, from 134 to 176)
342 for fast SCR reaction (NO+NO₂+NH₃), with $C_{\text{NO}}^0 / C_{\text{NO}_2}^0 / C_{\text{NH}_3}^0 = 300/300/300,$
343 $300/300/600$ and $300/300/900$ ppm, and $T = 225, 250$ and 300 °C. The volume of catalyst
344 in the reactor was diluted with inert quartz until 2 ml in all experiments. The weight of
345 the catalyst and the feed stream flowrate as well as the outlet composition obtained for all
346 experiment are detailed in Tables S3, S4, S5 and S6 (supplementary material),
347 respectively.

348 *4.2. Estimation of kinetic parameters*

349 4.2.1. First approach for N₂O formation-decomposition reactions

350 As explained in design of experiments, the kinetic data obtained from experiments 1 to
 351 62 (sets 1 and 2) were analyzed independently, with the NO₂, NH₃ and N₂O species
 352 monitored during reactions V, VI and VII, as reported in Table 1. For this subsystem with
 353 only three reactions in the network, the following differential ordinary equations have to
 354 be solved:

$$355 \frac{dC_{\text{NH}_3}}{d[W/Q]} = -4r_V - 3r_{\text{VI}} \quad (21)$$

$$358 \frac{dC_{\text{NO}_2}}{d[W/Q]} = -3r_V - 4r_{\text{VI}} \quad (22)$$

$$360 \frac{dC_{\text{N}_2\text{O}}}{d[W/Q]} = \frac{7}{2}r_{\text{VI}} - 2r_{\text{VII}} \quad (20)$$

362 The kinetic constants were expressed as a function of temperature according to the
 363 Arrhenius's expression, in the following reparametrized form, which improves stability
 364 in the computational program,

$$366 k_j = k_{j,523} \cdot \exp\left(\frac{E_j}{R} \left(\frac{1}{523} - \frac{1}{T}\right)\right) \quad (23)$$

368 Similarly, the ammonia equilibrium constant with temperature is expressed as

$$370 K_{\text{NH}_3} = K_{\text{NH}_3,523} \cdot \exp\left(\frac{-\Delta H_j}{R} \left(\frac{1}{523} - \frac{1}{T}\right)\right) \quad (24)$$

372 To find the optimal parameters the following sum of squares of deviations between
 373 experimental and calculated values of concentration for each component has to be
 374 minimized, i.e.

$$376 \min \sum_{\forall i}^{\text{no. exp.}} (C_{i,\text{exp}} - C_{i,\text{calc}})^2 \rightarrow \text{optimal parameters} \quad (25)$$

378 The parameter estimation program was implemented in MATLAB R2014b. For the
 379 optimization procedure, different algorithms have been tested, resulting the Nelder-Mead

380 algorithm that provided higher stability. Once initial conditions and parameter values
381 defined, the optimization subroutine was launched for searching the optimal parameters
382 by solving the ordinary differential equations (21), (22) and (20); hence, the output NH₃,
383 NO₂ and N₂O concentrations are calculated and the objective equation (25) evaluated
384 until minimization. The optimal values of the resulting kinetic parameters are shown in
385 Table 3.

386 TABLE 3

387 Figure 1 shows the output NH₃, NO₂ and N₂O concentration versus space time, both
388 experimental (points) and calculated (lines). Graphs on the left correspond to experiments
389 with NH₃/NO₂ equimolar concentration in the feed stream, 300/300 ppm, at temperature
390 of 225, 250 and 300 °C. The good quality of fitting between data simulated by the reduced
391 kinetic model and experimental data observed in Figure 1, validates assumptions made
392 previously by substitution of reaction (8) by reaction (14), and inclusion of C_{NO_2} in
393 the kinetic equation (15), corresponding to reactions VI and VII (Table 1), respectively.

394 FIGURE 1

395 Similarly, graphs on right side of Figure 1 show the output NH₃, NO₂ and N₂O
396 concentration vs. space time for $C_{\text{NO}_2}^0 / C_{\text{NH}_3}^0 = 300/400$ ppm, at temperature of 225,
397 250 and 300 °C. A good fitting between calculated and experimental data can be seen for
398 all experiments in Figure 1, for both ratios, especially at the intermediate temperature of
399 250 °C. A parallel evolution is observed between NH₃ and NO₂ consumption and
400 formation of N₂O, whose concentration is practically maintained constant at high space
401 time. This suggests that N₂O is formed by reaction between NO₂ and NH₃, and that N₂O
402 decomposition is apparently negligible at these conditions. Also, curves of N₂O formation
403 seems not to be dependent of the reactant ratio in the feed stream, so that NO₂
404 consumption appears as the rate-controlling step of the reaction sub-network formed by
405 reactions V, VI and VII.

406 Some disagreement between calculated and experimental data is observed at 300 °C, for
407 space time in the range 0.5-1 (g cat.) h m⁻³, giving underestimated calculated values of
408 NO₂ and NH₃, as NO₂ is rapidly consumed for experiments with low space time. In case
409 internal diffusional resistances in the catalyst could be the cause of this deviation, this
410 internal mass transfer limitation will be estimated afterwards.

411 4.2.2. Kinetic parameters for the whole reaction network

412 Sets 3, 4, 5 and 6 of experiments in Table 2 enter NO and/or O₂ as reactant, this making
413 all reactions in the network to be running simultaneously. Thus, to estimate the kinetic
414 parameters of the whole system (7 reactions in Table 1), all 176 experimental data in the
415 design (Tables S1 to S6, supplementary material) should be treated in the statistical
416 analysis.

417 Parameter estimation was made using same methodology as defined in the previous
418 paragraph, but considering the ordinary differential equation system composed of
419 equations (17) to (20), in which the evolution of NH₃, NO, NO₂, and N₂O concentrations
420 is mathematically described, and maintaining equation (25) as the objective function to
421 be minimized. Kinetic parameters previously estimated for reactions V, VI and VII, were
422 used as initial values in this second step. Table 4 shows the obtained optimal estimated
423 parameters (preexponential factors and activation energies) for each reaction included in
424 the NO_x NH₃-SCR system. Also the confidence intervals for a 95% probability of the
425 activation energies are shown. It can be found a great similarity of estimated activation
426 energies for reactions V, VI and VII, with those estimated previously (Table 3) when the
427 subsystem considering only these three reactions was analyzed. However, difference of
428 some order of magnitude is observed in the preexponential factors as a consequence of
429 including new reaction rate terms in equations (17) and (19) relative to equations (21) and
430 (22).

431 **TABLE 4**

432 The comparison of the obtained activation energy values with those reported in literature
433 by other authors reveals a good agreement, especially for reactions III, IV and V. For the
434 standard SCR, the activation energy in this work resulted in 91.5 kJ mol⁻¹, similar to 89.1
435 obtained by Metkar et al. [10] for Cu/CHA, and 84.9 kJ mol⁻¹ by Olsson et al. [36] for
436 Cu/ZSM-5. For fast SCR, the value of 42,0 kJ mol⁻¹ resulted close but lower, compared
437 with 77.1 kJ mol⁻¹ [10] and 85.1 kJ mol⁻¹ [36]. Finally, for NO₂ SCR reaction an activation
438 energy value of 118.1 kJ mol⁻¹ was obtained, intermediate between 136.3 and 72.3 kJ
439 mol⁻¹ reported by Metkar et al. [10] and Olsson et al. [36], respectively.

440 There are not so many experimental runs under same operational conditions to draw
441 concentration vs. space time curves, as the design of experiments was built with the aim
442 of covering the most extended range of different variables. As an example, Figure 2
443 shows, for $T = 250$ °C, the outlet NO concentration curve calculated with the estimated
444 parameters of the model and disposable experimental data in the standard SCR reaction

445 for NO/NH₃ concentration ratios of 800/300, 300/300 and 300/800 ppm. Good fitting
446 between experimental and calculated concentrations is observed for this set of
447 experiments.

448 **FIGURE 2**

449 In order to verify the quality of fitting for the whole experimental design, the outlet NO
450 concentration calculated with optimal estimated parameters vs. experimental data are
451 represented in Figure 3, including standard SCR (experiments 63-98, Table S3), NO
452 oxidation (experiments 121-133, Table S5) and fast SCR reaction (experiments 134-176,
453 Table S6), achieved at all temperatures. An auxiliary diagonal has been drawn to facilitate
454 the evaluation of deviations, and different symbols (and colors in the electronic version)
455 for each series of experiments corresponding to different reactions.

456 **FIGURE 3**

457 Similarly, Figure 4 shows deviations between experimental outlet NH₃ concentrations
458 and calculated with the optimal estimated parameters, including NO₂ + NH₃ reactions
459 (experiments 1-62, Tables S1 and S2), standard SCR reaction (experiments 63-98, Table
460 S3), NH₃ oxidation (experiments 99-120, Table S4), and fast SCR reaction (experiments
461 134-176, Table S6), for all studied temperatures. Again, a good correlation between
462 experimental and calculated data can be observed for all studied reactions. A slightly
463 higher deviation is observed for data corresponding to NH₃ oxidation (red asterisk
464 symbol), although these experiments were achieved with ammonia initial concentration
465 until 5000 ppm, much higher than that needed for this component in the real diesel
466 automobile application.

467 **FIGURE 4**

468 Figure 5 shows calculated vs. experimental outlet NO₂ concentrations for 141
469 experiments, including the initial subsystem composed of reactions V, VI and VII
470 (experiments 1-62, Tables S1 and S2), standard SCR reaction where NO₂ is formed
471 (experiments 63-98, Table S3), and fast SCR reaction. In this case, an important deviation
472 is observed for the fast SCR reaction at lower temperature (225 °C), where estimated
473 concentration is overestimated, apparently with lower NO₂ disappearance than
474 experimental values.

475 **FIGURE 5**

476 Also the N₂O formation is analyzed in Figure 6, which represents the correlation between
477 estimated and experimental outlet N₂O concentrations for NO + NH₃ reactions
478 (experiments 1-62, Tables S1 and S2), NO oxidation (experiments 121-133, Table S5),
479 and fast SCR reaction (experiments 134-176, Table S6) for the studied range of
480 temperature. No so good regression as for previous components is observed for this
481 undesired subproduct of the NO_x NH₃-SCR system. This component was never fed in any
482 of the experimental runs. One must take into account the narrower range of variation of
483 N₂O (70 ppm), in comparison to the other components, namely NO, NH₃ and NO₂,
484 included in the feed stream with at least 300 ppm. Another reason of the lack of fitting
485 can be consequence of mathematical restrictions in the regression procedure, which is
486 considering same ponderation for all compounds when the objective function is
487 evaluated. Compounds in higher concentration contribute more importantly in the
488 optimization process, which tries to find best fitting for concentration of these
489 compounds, specifically NO and NH₃.

490 **FIGURE 6**

491 In order to assess the quality of the regression, an analysis of variance was performed.
492 Table 5 shows the most representative values of the analysis. The model is able to explain
493 a large percentage of the variation sources with a determination coefficient of $r^2 = 0.952$.
494 The F test results in a value much higher than that tabulated for a 99% probability ($F=2.3$),
495 so the proposed model for the NO_x NH₃-SCR system is consistent, and explains with good
496 statistical significance the evolution of NO, NH₃, NO₂ and N₂O concentrations for the
497 large number of experiments realized. The standard error calculated resulted in 1.3×10^{-3}
498 mol m⁻³, which is equivalent to 29 ppm.

499 **TABLE 5**

500 *4.3. Influence of mass transfer inside the catalyst particle*

501 The GHSV=90,000 h⁻¹ used in experimental runs corresponds to a linear velocity of gases
502 through the catalyst bed of 37 cm s⁻¹, which apparently assure the absence of mass transfer
503 control around the catalyst particle [70, 71]. However, due to high reaction rate under
504 some reaction conditions, the mass transport inside the pores of the catalyst should be
505 checked by determination of the Thiele modulus,

506

$$\phi = \frac{V_p}{S_p} \sqrt{\frac{r_i}{C_{A,s}} \frac{1}{D_{eff}}} \quad (26)$$

and the effectiveness factor,

$$\eta = \frac{3}{\phi} \left[\frac{1}{\tanh \phi} - \frac{1}{\phi} \right] \quad (27)$$

The maximum reaction rate value was determined for each of the seven considered reactions under the most unfavorable conditions. Table 6 shows the values of the Thiele modulus and effectiveness factor determined by equations (26) and (27), respectively. Our kinetic model predicts the highest reaction rates for reactions II (NO oxidation) and III (standard SCR), for which effectiveness factors of 0.961 and 0.960 are determined at 300 °C. For the remaining reactions, the estimated effectiveness factor resulted in values higher than 0.998. Therefore, with effectiveness factors greater than 0.96, the internal diffusion control can be considered negligible up to 300 °C.

At 350 °C, the reaction rate of the standard SCR reaction increases notably, resulting in an estimated effectiveness factor of 0.844. At these conditions, the concentration gradients inside the catalyst particle begins to be appreciable, at least at the reactor inlet where reaction rate is maximum; however, when reactant concentration is decreasing along the reactor intraparticle gradients are progressively decreasing to negligible values, even at 350 °C. The estimated effectiveness factor resulted in values above 0.95 for all reactions in the proposed kinetic model, validating the assumption of negligible intraparticle diffusional control, practically under all experimental conditions managed in this work for kinetic parameter estimation.

TABLE 6

5. Conclusions

A steady-state global kinetic model for the NO_x NH₃-SCR reaction system in excess of oxygen has been proposed. The overall kinetic model consists of the following reactions: (I) NH₃ oxidation, (II) NO oxidation, (III) standard SCR reaction, (IV) fast SCR reaction, (V) NO₂ SCR reaction, (VI) N₂O formation and (VII) N₂O decomposition. The proposed kinetic scheme postulates a Langmuir-Hinshelwood formalism between adsorbed ammonia and weakly adsorbed NO species, which simplifies to Rideal-Eley reaction rate equations with only ammonia adsorbed and NO reacting directly from the gas phase.

539 An initial set of 62 experiments were designed, with only NO₂ and NH₃ in the feed stream
540 that allowed to get a first estimation of kinetic parameters of reactions V, VI and VII, and
541 considering nearly inexistence of reactions I to IV because of the absence NO and O₂ in
542 the feed stream. The parameter estimation mathematical program was implemented in
543 Matlab R2014b, and minimization —by the Nelder-Mead algorithm— of the sum of
544 squares of deviation between experimental and calculated NO, NH₃, NO₂, N₂O
545 concentrations was derived by solution of the material balance ordinary differential
546 equation system. The proposed model resulted in a good agreement between calculated
547 and experimental NH₃ and NO₂ concentrations at the outlet, for initial concentrations of
548 300/300 and 400/300 ppm, temperatures of 225, 250 and 300 °C, and space times (W/Q)
549 up to 8 (g cat.) h m⁻³. This range pretends to cover operational conditions simulating the
550 real application for NO_x removal of diesel and lean mixture engines aftertreatment
551 systems.

552 The introduction of NO activates all the seven reactions of the proposed global NO_x NH₃-
553 SCR system. Additional extensive experimentation was designed up to a total of 176
554 experiments, including NO oxidation, NH₃ oxidation, standard SCR reaction and fast
555 SCR reaction. Same mathematical procedure as before was used for finding the optimal
556 estimated parameters, namely activation energy and frequency factors, for each reaction
557 in the model, including adsorption energy of ammonia. The optimal activation energies
558 resulted in 91.5, 42.0, and 118 kJ mol⁻¹, for the standard, fast and NO₂ SCR reactions,
559 respectively.

560 The determination coefficient of the proposed global kinetic model resulted in 0.952 with
561 great statistical significance, with the F test calculated for a probability of 99% more than
562 a hundred times that statistically tabulated. The outlet concentrations of major reactants
563 in the NO_x NH₃-SCR system —NO, NH₃ and NO₂— result accurately estimated by the
564 model, with the exception of an overestimated NO₂ concentration for the fast SCR
565 reaction at the lower temperature of 225 °C (good for higher temperatures).

566 Some limitation has been found in the optimal estimation of the undesired N₂O
567 subproduct in the NO_x NH₃-SCR system, due to low formation levels under the studied
568 conditions, which apparently reduces the weight of these experimental data in the global
569 parameter estimation procedure. Also, experimental error for so low concentrations can
570 be expected to be higher. In any case, the model is able to fit relatively well an important
571 number of experiments.

572 We are nowadays including the global model proposed in this paper, in new computer
 573 programs to simulate the behavior of the NO_x NH₃-SCR system in real aftertreatment
 574 catalytic converters in the form of washcoated monoliths under one- or multidimensional
 575 reactor models, where diffusional resistances and different flow behavior need to be
 576 considered. This, which will be the aim of a following paper, will allow predicting the
 577 catalyst performance in terms of the washcoat characteristics as well as operational
 578 variables, especially temperature window performance.

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584

585 **Nomenclature**

586	$C_{i, \text{exp}}$	Concentration of i species experimentally determined, mol m ⁻³ .
587	$C_{i, \text{calc}}$	Concentration of i species calculated in the kinetic model, mol m ⁻³ .
588	$C_{i, s}$	Concentration of i species in the surface, mol m ⁻³ .
589	$D_{i, \text{eff}}$	Effective diffusion of I element in gaseous mixture, m ² s ⁻¹ .
590	E_j	Activation energy of reaction j, kJ mol ⁻¹ .
591	k_j	Kinetic rate constants of reaction j, units in Table 4
592	k_j^0	Pre-exponential coefficient in Arrhenius equation of reaction j, units of k_j .
593	K_{NH_3}	Equilibrium constant of NH ₃ adsorption-desorption, m ³ mol ⁻¹ .
594	$K_{\text{NO}}^{\text{eq}}$	Equilibrium constant of NO oxidation reaction, m ^{1.5} mol ^{-0.5} .
595	$n_{i,j}$	Stoichiometric coefficient of element i in reaction j.
596	Q	Flow rate, m ³ s ⁻¹ .
597	R	Ideal gas constant, 8,314 J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹ .
598	r_j	Rate of reaction j, mol g ⁻¹ h ⁻¹ .
599	S_p	Pore surface, m ² .
600	T	Temperature, °C.
601	V_p	Total pore volume, cm ³ g ⁻¹ .
602	W	Catalyst weight, g.
603	W/Q	Space time, (g cat.) h m ⁻³ .

604 *Greek symbols*

605 ΔH_j Heat of reaction j , kJ mol^{-1} .

606 $\theta_{\text{NH}_3}^j$ Surface coverage of adsorbed NH_3 at site j .

607 ϕ Thiele module

608 η Effectiveness factor

609

610

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730 **Table and Figure captions**

731

732 Table 1. SCR reaction network and kinetic expressions.

733 Table 2. Design of experiments, total = 176 experiments, distributed into six categories
734 according to different compounds in feed stream for analyzing different
735 reactions included in the SCR network shown in Table 1.

736 Table 3. Optimal kinetic parameters estimated from nonlinear regression of experimental
737 data corresponding to reactions V, VI and VII (Table 1), experiments 1-62
738 (Table 2).

739 Table 4. Optimal kinetic parameters from nonlinear regression of all experimental data
740 (176 experiments, Table 2) to the global kinetic model based on the seven
741 reactions proposed for the NO_x NH₃-SCR system (reactions I-VII, equations.
742 3.1-3.7).

743 Table 5. Analysis of variance for the regression of the proposed global kinetic model.

744 Table 6. Estimated values of the Thiele module and the effectiveness factor for each of
745 the stages of the globalized model, under the most unfavorable reaction
746 conditions in each case.

747

748 Figure 1. Experimental and calculated evolution of NH₃, NO₂ and N₂O concentration
749 with space time for the subsystem including reactions V, VI and VI. Left side
750 graphs: inlet NH₃/NO₂ concentration ratio, 300/300 ppm (experiments 1-29,
751 Table S1). Right side graphs: inlet NH₃/NO₂ concentration ratio, 400/300
752 ppm (experiments 30-62, Table S2).

753 Figure 2. Experimental and calculated evolution of NO concentration with space time
754 in the standard SCR reaction for inlet NO/NH₃ concentration ratios of
755 800/300, 300/300 and 300/800 ppm (numbers on each point correspond to
756 experimental data in Table S3).

757 Figure 3. Outlet NO concentration calculated from the proposed global model vs.
758 experimental data obtained for NO oxidation (crosses, experiments 121-133,
759 Table S5), standard SCR reaction (solid triangles, experiments 63-98, Table

760 S3), and fast SCR reaction (empty squares, experiments 134-176, Table S6).
761 All studied temperatures are included.

762 Figure 4. Outlet NH_3 concentration calculated from the proposed global model vs.
763 experimental data obtained for $\text{NO}_2 + \text{NH}_3$ reactions (empty circles,
764 experiments 1-62, Tables S1 and S2), NH_3 oxidation (asterisk, experiments
765 99-120, Table S4), standard SCR reaction (solid triangles, experiments 63-
766 98, Table S3), and fast SCR reaction (empty squares, experiments 134-176,
767 Table S6). All studied temperatures are included.

768 Figure 5. Outlet NO_2 concentration calculated from the proposed global model vs.
769 experimental data obtained for $\text{NO}_2 + \text{NH}_3$ reactions (empty circles,
770 experiments 1-62, Tables S1 and S2), NO oxidation (crosses, experiments
771 121-133, Table S5), standard SCR reaction (solid triangles, experiments 63-
772 98, Table S3), and fast SCR reaction (empty squares, experiments 134-176,
773 Table S6). All studied temperatures are included.

774 Figure 6. Outlet N_2O concentration calculated from the proposed global model vs.
775 experimental data obtained for $\text{NO}_2 + \text{NH}_3$ reactions (empty circles,
776 experiments 1-62, Tables S1 and S2), NO oxidation (crosses, experiments
777 121-133, Table S5), and fast SCR reaction (empty squares, experiments 134-
778 176, Table S6). All studied temperatures are included.

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780

781

TABLE 1

Reaction	Kinetic equation
I. $\text{NH}_3 + 3/4 \text{O}_2 \rightarrow 1/2 \text{N}_2 + 3/2 \text{H}_2\text{O}$	$r_{\text{I}} = \frac{k_{\text{I}} C_{\text{NH}_3} C_{\text{O}_2}}{1 + K_{\text{NH}_3} C_{\text{NH}_3}}$
II. $\text{NO} + 1/2 \text{O}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{NO}_2$	$r_{\text{II}} = k_{\text{II}} (C_{\text{NO}} C_{\text{O}_2}^{0.5} - C_{\text{NO}_2} / K_{\text{NO}}^{\text{eq.}})$
III. $\text{NH}_3 + \text{NO} + 1/4 \text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{N}_2 + 3/2 \text{H}_2\text{O}$	$r_{\text{III}} = \frac{k_{\text{III}} C_{\text{NH}_3} C_{\text{NO}} C_{\text{O}_2}}{1 + K_{\text{NH}_3} C_{\text{NH}_3}}$
IV. $2 \text{NH}_3 + \text{NO} + \text{NO}_2 \rightarrow 2 \text{N}_2 + 3 \text{H}_2\text{O}$	$r_{\text{IV}} = \frac{k_{\text{IV}} C_{\text{NH}_3} C_{\text{NO}} C_{\text{NO}_2}}{1 + K_{\text{NH}_3} C_{\text{NH}_3}}$
V. $4 \text{NH}_3 + 3 \text{NO}_2 \rightarrow 7/2 \text{N}_2 + 6 \text{H}_2\text{O}$	$r_{\text{V}} = \frac{k_{\text{V}} C_{\text{NH}_3} C_{\text{NO}_2}}{1 + K_{\text{NH}_3} C_{\text{NH}_3}}$
VI. $3 \text{NH}_3 + 4 \text{NO}_2 \rightarrow 7/2 \text{N}_2\text{O} + 9/2 \text{H}_2\text{O}$	$r_{\text{VI}} = \frac{k_{\text{VI}} C_{\text{NH}_3} C_{\text{NO}_2}}{1 + K_{\text{NH}_3} C_{\text{NH}_3}}$
VII. $2 \text{N}_2\text{O} \rightarrow 2 \text{N}_2 + \text{O}_2$	$r_{\text{VII}} = k_{\text{VII}} C_{\text{N}_2\text{O}} C_{\text{NO}_2}$

TABLE 2

Set	Reaction	W, g cat.	Q, l min ⁻¹	C _{NO} ⁰ , ppm	C _{NO₂} ⁰ , ppm	C _{NH₃} ⁰ , ppm	C _{O₂} ⁰ , %	T, °C	Experiments
1	NO ₂ +NH ₃	0.05-0.5	1-3.1	-	300	300	-	225-350	1 to 29
2	NO ₂ +NH ₃	0.05-0.5	1-3.1	-	300	400	-	225-350	30 to 62
3	NO+NH ₃ +O ₂	0.5	1-3.3	300, 800	-	300, 800	6	225-350	63 to 98
4	NH ₃ +O ₂	0.01-0.5	1-3.3	-	-	300-5000	6	225-300	99 to 120
5	NO+O ₂	0.5	1.56	200, 330	-	-	6	150-500	121 to 133
6	NO+NO ₂ +NH ₃	0.05-0.5	1-3.2	300	300	300, 600, 900	-	225-300	134 to 176

TABLE 3

Parameter	Activation energy, kJ mol ⁻¹	Preexponential factor	
		Value	Units
k_V	132.5	8.64×10^{15}	$\text{m}^6 \text{g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$
k_{VI}	145.0	3.77×10^{17}	$\text{m}^6 \text{g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$
k_{VII}	249.9	1.29×10^{27}	$\text{m}^6 \text{g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$
K_{NH_3}	99.23 ^a	7.57×10^{-7}	$\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$

^a In the case of NH₃ adsorption, this value corresponds to the adsorption process enthalpy (Eq. 24).

TABLE 4

Kinetic constant	Preexponential factor		Activation energy, kJ mol ⁻¹	Confidence interval (95%)
	Value	Units		
k_I	1.59×10^{12}	$\text{m}^6 \text{g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$	108.11	± 0.40
k_{II}	6.81×10^5	$\text{m}^{4.5} \text{m}^{-3} \text{h}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-0.5}$	12.39	± 3.01
k_{III}	1.09×10^{12}	$\text{m}^9 \text{g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-2}$	91.45	± 1.58
k_{IV}	9.40×10^9	$\text{m}^9 \text{g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-2}$	41.98	± 1.15
k_V	3.07×10^{12}	$\text{m}^6 \text{g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$	118.10	± 29.21
k_{VI}	4.48×10^{18}	$\text{m}^6 \text{g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$	152.34	± 1.44
k_{VII}	2.45×10^{28}	$\text{m}^6 \text{g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$	257.92	± 6.16
K_{NH_3}	7.66×10^{-7}	$\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$	99.19 ^a	-
$K_{\text{NO}}^{\text{eq}}$	8.61×10^{-4}	$\text{m}^{1.5} \text{mol}^{-0.5}$	57.28 ^a	-

^aIn the case of NH₃ and NO, this values correspond to the enthalpies of the adsorption process and the oxidation reaction, respectively.

TABLE 5

Error source	Sum squares	Freedom degrees	Mean square	F	Probability
Regression	5.58×10^{-3}	14	3.98×10^{-4}	226.1	>99.9%
Residual	2.84×10^{-4}	161	1.76×10^{-6}		
Total	5.86×10^{-3}	175			

TABLE 6

Reaction	$T = 300\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$		$T = 350\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$	
	Thiele	Effectiveness	Thiele	Effectiveness
	module	factor	module	factor
	(ϕ)	(η)	(ϕ)	(η)
$\text{NH}_3 + 3/4\text{O}_2 \rightarrow 1/2\text{N}_2 + 3/2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	0.14	0.999	0.34	0.992
$\text{NO} + 1/2\text{O}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{NO}_2$	0.78	0.961	0.87	0.953
$\text{NH}_3 + \text{NO} + 1/4\text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{N}_2 + 3/2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	0.80	0.960	1.73	0.844
$2\text{NH}_3 + \text{NO} + \text{NO}_2 \rightarrow 2\text{N}_2 + 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	0.12	0.999	0.18	0.998
$4\text{NH}_3 + 3\text{NO}_2 \rightarrow 7/2\text{N}_2 + 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	0.005	1.000	0.014	1.000
$3\text{NH}_3 + 4\text{NO}_2 \rightarrow 7/2\text{N}_2\text{O} + 9/2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	0.18	0.998	0.64	0.974
$2\text{N}_2\text{O} \rightarrow 2\text{N}_2 + \text{O}_2$	0.10	0.999	0.84	0.956

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**Steady-state NH₃-SCR global model and kinetic
parameter estimation for NO_x removal in diesel
engine exhaust aftertreatment with Cu/chabazite**

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16 Keywords:

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NH₃-SCR, NO_x removal, kinetic model, parameter estimation, Cu/CHA, chabazite

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zeolite

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23 **Abstract**

24 A steady-state global kinetic model for the NO_x NH_3 -SCR reaction system, including
25 NH_3 oxidation, NO oxidation, standard SCR reaction, fast SCR reaction, NO_2 SCR
26 reaction, and N_2O formation and decomposition is proposed, based on the Eley-Rideal
27 formalism in which only ammonia is adsorbed and NO reacts directly from the gas
28 phase. The experimental runs were designed under operational conditions simulating
29 NO, NH_3 , NO_2 feed stream composition near to the real application for NO_x removal
30 from diesel engine automobile exhaust aftertreatment. An initial set of 62 experiments,
31 with only NO_2 and NH_3 in the feed stream allows a preliminary estimation of some
32 kinetic parameters. Additional extensive experimentation up to 176 runs under a wide
33 range of feed stream composition, temperature and space time was carried out. The
34 experimental outlet NO, NH_3 , NO_2 and N_2O concentrations are analyzed for kinetic
35 parameter estimation of seven reactions included in the proposed global NO_x NH_3 -SCR
36 system, resulting in activation energy values for standard SCR reaction, fast SCR
37 reaction and NO_2 SCR reaction of 91.5, 42.0, and 118 kJ mol^{-1} , respectively. The
38 proposed model resulted of high statistical significance deduced from the analysis of
39 variance, with a determination coefficient of 0.952, and excellent F-test for a probability
40 superior to 99%.

41 **1. Introduction**

42 The selective catalytic reduction (SCR) by NH₃ has been considered for many years the
43 most efficient control technology to remove noxious environmental NO_x emissions
44 from chemical plants and stationary power sources, mainly achieved on Mo- or W-
45 promoted V₂O₅-TiO₂ catalysts [1-4]. In 2005, the SCR technology was brought to the
46 market for heavy duty vehicles already, based on the use of similar formulation on
47 honeycomb monolith catalysts [5]. However, the low stability of vanadia at high
48 temperature and more and more stricter NO_x emission regulations for both heavy and
49 low duty vehicles, which requires higher activity at low temperature, have motivated the
50 introduction of zeolite-based catalysts promoted by transition metals, as iron [6-8] and
51 copper [9-15].

52 The most extensive studies have been carried out on Cu²⁺ ion-exchanged ZSM-5
53 (Cu/ZSM-5) zeolites, first shown to achieve high NO decomposition rates and NO_x
54 SCR activity [6, 13, 16]. Later, Cu²⁺ ion-exchanged beta zeolite (Cu/beta) was shown to
55 have excellent NO_x NH₃-SCR activity with better hydrothermal stability than ZSM-5
56 catalysts [12, 17]. Yet, none of these zeolites show durability sufficient for the
57 automotive industry. In the year 2010, Cu²⁺-exchanged molecular sieves with chabazite
58 (CHA) structures, for example, Cu/SSZ-13 and Cu/SAPO-34, have been discovered to
59 show apparently much improved activity, selectivity, and durability for exhausts
60 aftertreatment in diesel and lean burn engines [18-21].

61 We and other researchers compared SCR activities and hydrothermal stabilities of
62 Cu/CHA with other Cu²⁺ ion-exchanged zeolites, especially Cu/ZSM-5 and Cu/beta [14,
63 18, 19]. Indeed, Cu/CHA shows comparable or even higher activity, higher N₂
64 selectivity and most impressively, much higher hydrothermal stability even under harsh
65 conditions; for example, extended hydrothermal treatments at 1073 K.

66 The standard SCR reaction between NO and NH₃ occurs in the presence of oxygen:

68 Many studies have shown that the NO_x reduction activity increases if NO and NO₂ are
69 fed in equimolecular amount [22]. The reaction between equimolecular amounts of NO
70 and NO₂ with NH₃ is known as the fast SCR reaction:

72 The third important reaction in this chemistry is NO₂ SCR reaction:

74 This reaction is important when the fed NO_x comprises mostly NO₂. While the presence
75 of NO₂ accelerates the NO_x reduction rate on various catalysts [22], its presence
76 complicates the overall NH₃-SCR reaction chemistry [23]. NO₂ has been proposed as
77 the key species for the SCR of NO_x with NH₃ on various zeolite catalysts, and the
78 oxidation of NO to NO₂ is the likely rate-limiting step [24]. Stevenson et al. [25] and
79 Wallin et al. [26] argued that oxidation of NO is the rate determining step in the
80 reduction of NO by NH₃ on H-ZSM-5. Many other studies have focused on the
81 mechanistic issues for the SCR chemistry. Komatsu et al. [27] suggested a mechanism
82 for the standard SCR reaction on Cu-zeolite catalysts that involves the formation of a
83 bridging NO₃ molecule which further reacts with NO to form NO₂. The NO₂ then reacts
84 with NH₃ to produce N₂ and H₂O. Other studies presented a mechanistic model in which
85 the preferred path for NO_x reduction with ammonia occurs via ammonium nitrite, which
86 decomposes to N₂ and H₂O [28]; and others have suggested that the reduction of NO
87 and NO₂ by NH₃ involves the formation of HNO₂ and HNO₃ [29, 30]. We tried to
88 understand the role of the different copper species on the activity of Cu/H-ZSM-5 and
89 Cu/H-BETA catalysts in the NH₃-SCR process for NO_x removal in a wide temperature
90 range (140–500 °C) [12], suggesting that the nature of the copper species affects the
91 SCR behavior of catalyst. CuO clusters promote NO reduction at low temperature
92 whereas isolated Cu(II) ions maintain high NO_x conversion at high temperatures. In
93 addition, catalysts with low CuO content exhibit higher N₂ selectivity, since CuO
94 promotes the formation of N₂O and NO₂. Unlike hydrothermally treated Cu/ZSM-5 and
95 Cu/BETA catalysts, minor changes in the copper sites were observed on Cu/SSZ-13,
96 which was consistent with the minor changes in the SCR activity of the Cu/SSZ-13
97 catalyst after the hydrothermal treatment process [14, 31, 32].

98 In spite of a host of experimental studies focused on mechanistic issues and reaction
99 pathways, a much smaller number of studies have focused on the kinetic modeling of
100 NH₃-SCR reactions. Several studies presented steady-state global kinetic models for the
101 standard SCR for vanadia-based catalysts [1, 33, 34], Cu/ZSM-5 [35, 36] and
102 Cu/faujasite [37]. Nova et al. [38, 39] developed a detailed transient kinetic model,
103 while Chatterjee et al. [40-42] developed a global kinetic model for both vanadia- and
104 Fe/zeolite catalysts. Their model describes well the transient and steady-state NO_x

105 conversion and the effect of feed NO/NO₂ ratio on the NH₃-SCR chemistry. Olsson and
106 coworkers developed both global and detailed kinetic models for NH₃-SCR reactions on
107 Fe/ZSM-5 and Cu/ZSM-5 catalysts [36, 43-46]. Their kinetic models account for
108 transient effects for various feed concentrations of NO₂. To our knowledge, there is no
109 kinetic model available for the recently commercialized small pore Cu/CHA catalyst,
110 with the exception of the 1+1 dimensional reactor model presented by Metkar et al.
111 [10], which includes external transport and washcoat diffusion processes. According to
112 our previous work [14], Cu/CHA achieves superior performance in the NO NH₃-SCR
113 reaction, with practically 100% NO conversion from 220 to 380 °C. At higher
114 temperatures, the presence of water in the feed stream may even improve NO
115 conversion at higher temperatures due to the inhibition of ammonia oxidation, whereas
116 small differences are observed in the low-medium temperature range. In contrast,
117 Cu/ZSM-5 and Cu/BETA suffer from significant destruction of surface area, acidity and
118 surface reducibility with hydrothermal aging, causing notable decrease in their catalytic
119 performance.

120 The main objective of the current study is to develop a global kinetic model that
121 predicts the main features of various NO/NO₂/NH₃ reactions occurring during NH₃-
122 SCR on Cu/chabazite (CHA). The kinetic model considers ammonia adsorption and
123 desorption, NH₃ oxidation, NO oxidation, standard SCR, fast SCR, NO₂ SCR, N₂O
124 formation and N₂O decomposition. The model is deduced from an extended set of
125 experiments carried out under conditions simulating the automobile application, but
126 with powdered catalyst in the absence of diffusional control, and with validation under
127 an extended temperature range, i.e. 225-350 °C. The model is intended to be as simple
128 as possible to be implemented in mathematical modeling of washcoated honeycombs
129 under one- or multidimensional reactor models, which allow predicting improvements
130 of the catalyst performance in terms of the washcoat characteristics as well as the
131 temperature performance windows.

132

133 **2. The SCR reaction network**

134 A completed, detailed description of the NH₃-SCR technology can be found in the
135 recent book of Nova and Tronconi [47], including mechanistic aspects and reaction

136 kinetics for Cu/zeolite catalysts [48]. Both fundamental detailed kinetic models as well
137 as more globalized models have been discussed in literature [36, 39, 41, 44].

138 In addition to the three main reactions already mentioned as standard SRC (reaction 1),
139 fast SCR (reaction 2), and NO₂ SCR (reaction 3) to produce nitrogen, also a number of
140 secondary reactions occurs leading to undesired consumption of NH₃ or generation of
141 subproducts as N₂O, NH₄NO₃ and HNO₃. The oxidation of NH₃ is an important lateral
142 reaction which occurs mainly at temperature higher than 350 °C, not desirable as it
143 decreases availability of NH₃ needed for reactions (1)-(3),

145 On the other hand, the oxidation of NO to NO₂ reaches equilibrium conditions at
146 temperature 150-200 °C that are decreasing with increasing temperature (exothermic
147 reaction):

149 Reaction (5) is desirable as NO₂ is reduced with NH₃ more efficiently than NO (fast vs.
150 standard SCR reactions); on the contrary, the existence of NO₂ makes more complex the
151 reaction network.

152 N₂O is an unwanted by-product during the SCR process over copper zeolites that
153 increases with the NO₂ content. The mechanism for the N₂O production is suggested to
154 be from the decomposition of ammonium nitrate above 200 °C, the later formed by
155 reaction of ammonia with NO₂:

158 In fact, combination of reactions (6) and (7) yields to another NO₂ SCR reaction
159 producing undesirable N₂O to be considered in the SCR system.

161 On the other hand, N₂O decomposes into N₂ and O₂ at higher temperatures (reaction 9),
162 as already reported by several authors [49-51] on MFI, BEA and FAU zeolites doped
163 with Fe, Cu and Co. The samples activity depends on the introduced transition metal
164 and the following order of their activation effect: Cu > Co > Fe was observed [52].

166

167 **3. Experimental**

168 *3.1. Catalyst preparation*

169 First, N,N,N-trimethyl-1-adamantammonium (TMAda) was prepared for its use as
170 organic structure directing agent (OSDA) in the synthesis of chabazite. For this purpose,
171 29.6 g of 1-Adamantamine (Sigma-Aldrich) and 64 g of potassium carbonate (Sigma-
172 Aldrich) were mixed with 320 ml of chloroform. Then, 75 g of methyl iodide was added
173 dropwise while the reaction was stirred in an ice bath. The reaction was maintained for
174 5 days under agitation at room temperature. The mixture was filtered and washed with
175 diethyl ether, and the resultant solid further extracted with chloroform. The final product
176 was N,N,N-trimethyl-1-adamantammonium iodide. This iodide salt was anion
177 exchanged using an ion exchange resin, and finally, an aqueous solution of the
178 hydroxide form of TMAda was achieved (7.6% wt).

179 Chabazite zeolite was prepared following the former synthesis description reported by
180 Zones [53]. In this sense, 1.45 g of sodium hydroxide (Sigma-Aldrich, 98%) was
181 dissolved in 99.9 g of an aqueous solution of N,N,N-trimethyl-1-adamantammonium
182 hydroxide (7.6% wt), and the mixture was maintained under stirring for 15 minutes.
183 Then, 1.0 g of aluminum hydroxide (66% wt, Sigma-Aldrich) and 10.9 g of fumed silica
184 (aerosil) were introduced in the synthesis mixture, and maintained under stirring the
185 required time to evaporate the solvent until the desired gel concentration. The final gel
186 composition was SiO₂:0.037 Al₂O₃:0.20 TMAda:0.20 NaOH:18.3 H₂O. The gel was
187 transferred to an autoclave with a Teflon liner, and heated at 150 °C for 5 days under
188 dynamic conditions. The sample after hydrothermal crystallization was filtered and
189 washed with abundant distilled water, and finally dried at 100 °C. Finally, CHA zeolite
190 was calcined at 580 °C for 4 h.

191 Ion exchange (IE) was the method used for preparing the Cu-exchanged CHA zeolite.
192 The sample was first washed with a 0.04 M aqueous solution of NaNO₃ (~150 ml/g of
193 zeolite). Then, the Cu IE was conducted using an aqueous solution of Cu(CH₃CO₂)₂
194 containing the required amount of Cu. The liquid to solid ratio was fixed at 100 ml/g of
195 zeolite, and the resultant mixture was maintained under stirring overnight at room
196 temperature. Finally, the sample was filtered and washed with distilled water, and
197 calcined at 550 °C for 4 h. The prepared powdered catalysts were then pelletized,

198 crushed and sieved to 0.3-0.5 mm. Previous experiments carried out with different
199 particle size catalysts revealed that mass transfer limitations could be considered
200 negligible, so that internal diffusion in the catalyst particle was not the rate-controlling
201 step in the kinetic mechanism for this particle size of 0.3-0.5 mm.

202 The actual chemical compositions of the powdered Cu/CHA zeolite resulted in Si/Al
203 ratio of 10.6 and a loading of 3.9% Cu, which was used for kinetic experiments.

204 *3.2. Reaction and product analysis setup*

205 The experiments were performed in a vertical downflow stainless steel reactor. The
206 reactor tube, 13 mm inner diameter, was placed into a 3-zone tube furnace. In order to
207 obtain kinetic data for extended range of space times, experiments were performed with
208 $C_{\text{NO}} = C_{\text{NO}_2} = C_{\text{NH}_3} = 300 \text{ ppm}$ and $C_{\text{O}_2} = 6\%$, different catalyst weight and total feed
209 flow, varying from 0.05 to 0.5 g and 1.0 to 3.3 l min⁻¹, respectively. Typical reactant
210 concentrations used for experimental runs were but also these values were extensively
211 varied when the effect of every reactant were observed (see Supplementary Material,
212 later for every experimental data set). The presence of water in feed stream was not
213 included in the kinetic analysis. The reactor was filled with the corresponding weight of
214 catalyst until a volume of 2 ml, being diluted with inert quartz ground at the same
215 particle size than catalyst (300-500 μm). All the lines of the installation were heated at
216 200 °C avoiding NH₄NO₃ formation which decomposed at this temperature into N₂O
217 and H₂O by reaction (7). This fact has been verified by good closing of N-compounds
218 balance in an initial set of experiments.

219 Gases (NO, NO₂, NH₃, O₂ and Ar) were fed via mass flow controllers. Argon was used
220 as inert gas, allowing analysis of nitrogen at the exit gas. The outlet gas concentrations
221 were continuously measured using a MKS MultiGas 2030 FT-IR analyzer followed by a
222 MKS Cirrus quadrupole MS on line. NO, NO₂, NH₃, N₂O and H₂O were quantitatively
223 monitored by the FT-IR analyzer, whereas H₂, N₂ and O₂ were monitored by the MS
224 analyzer. The N-compounds mass balances in experimental data closed under 5%-error
225 for all experimental runs.

226 *3.3. Kinetic model*

227 Taking into account the SCR reaction network above described, we chose initially the
228 reaction mechanism described by the following reactions: i) ammonia oxidation
229 (reaction 4), ii) NO oxidation (reaction 5), iii) standard SCR (reaction 1), iv) fast SCR

230 (reaction 2), v) NO₂ SCR (reaction 3), vi) N₂O formation (reaction 8), and vii) N₂O
 231 decomposition (reaction 9). As already mentioned, ammonium nitrates are not
 232 considered in the scheme as they decomposed directly into N₂O and H₂O at 200 °C, at
 233 which temperature all lines are heated in the experimental setup.

234 A good description of the ammonia storage and desorption is critical in order to
 235 describe transient features of the SCR system. Detailed kinetic models for ammonia
 236 adsorption and desorption usually use a Temkin type of kinetics that considers
 237 adsorbate-adsorbate interactions [44, 54] in line with previous proposals for V-based
 238 catalysts [55, 56]. In the case of global models, Langmuir-Hinshelwood [35, 57] or
 239 Eley-Rideal [25, 58] models are usually assumed for the kinetic equations, considering
 240 that both NH₃ and NO are adsorbed on the catalyst active sites (Langmuir-
 241 Hinshelwood) or that NH₃ is adsorbed but NO reacts directly from the gas phase (Eley-
 242 Rideal). We have initially postulated that the kinetics obeys an Eley-Rideal formalism
 243 between gaseous NO and adsorbed NH₃, or better a Langmuir-Hinshelwood formalism
 244 with weakly adsorbed NO species [43, 59-62]. If ammonia adsorption and desorption
 245 are in equilibrium,

247 the fraction of sites adsorbed of ammonia will be related to ammonia concentration by a
 248 Langmuir-Hinshelwood expression:

$$249 \quad \theta_{\text{NH}_3\text{-S}_1} = \frac{K_{\text{NH}_3} C_{\text{NH}_3}}{1 + K_{\text{NH}_3} C_{\text{NH}_3}} \quad (11)$$

250 where K_{NH_3} is the ammonia adsorption equilibrium constant. With this assumption we
 251 can describe the SCR kinetic equations for steps I, III, IV, V and VI, as listed in Table
 252 1.

253 The NO to NO₂ oxidation reaction (step II in Table 1) has been considered in
 254 equilibrium in the gas phase, without the participation of any adsorbed species, being
 255 described by

$$256 \quad r_{\text{II}} = k_{\text{II}} (C_{\text{NO}} C_{\text{O}_2}^{0.5} - C_{\text{NO}_2} / K_{\text{NO}}^{\text{eq}}) \quad (12)$$

257 The equilibrium constant has been determined thermodynamically from the formation
 258 heats of the components NO and NO₂, resulting in

$$259 \quad K_{\text{NO}}^{\text{eq.}} = 8.31 \times 10^{-4} \exp\left(\frac{5728}{RT}\right) \quad (13)$$

260 For the N₂O decomposition (reaction VII in Table 1), different mechanisms have been
 261 proposed in the literature [50, 63-67] in which N₂O reacts from the gas phase and
 262 generating N₂ in the gas phase and O ad-atom on the catalyst. Then two adjacent O ad-
 263 atoms conform O₂ in the gas phase. More recent microkinetic schemes based in DFT
 264 [67], have suggested a more complex scheme for the formation of O₂, with a higher
 265 number of elementary steps; and transient studies in TAP reactor [66] indicates that the
 266 reaction mechanism is not influenced neither for the metal species in the catalyst nor for
 267 its incorporation method.

268 An initial set of experiments was realized with NO₂ and NH₃, but neither NO nor O₂ in
 269 feed stream (Table S1, supplementary material), as then only reactions (3), (8) and (9)
 270 are involved in the reduced reaction network. In fact, this experimental data set will be
 271 firstly kinetically analyzed later in the paper. However, qualitative observation of data
 272 reveals more disappearance of NO₂ than NH₃, opposite to that expected when
 273 considering reactions (3) and (8), which predict more consumption of NH₃ than NO₂
 274 and even consumption, respectively. With the aim of approaching the model to
 275 experimental observation, we considered less NO₂ reduction by reaction (8), remaining
 276 unreduced N₂O as product,

278 This reaction has already been described in literature at temperatures below 350 °C for
 279 NH₃-SCR on zeolite-based catalysts [68, 69]. Then, reaction (8) can be removed from
 280 the kinetic scheme, as it is equivalent to linear combination of reactions (3) and (14),
 281 providing stoichiometry as experimentally observed. In fact, experimental data (Table
 282 S1) fit with high significance the proposed, reduced kinetic model (see later).

283 Additionally, a best fitting of the experimental data sets in Table S1 (experiments 1 to
 284 62, supplementary material), demanded us to include in the kinetic equation
 285 corresponding to N₂O decomposition C_{N₂O} (reaction 9) not only C_{NO₂} but also, resulting
 286 in the following expression:

$$287 \quad r_{\text{VII}} = k_{\text{VII}} C_{\text{N}_2\text{O}} C_{\text{NO}_2} \quad (15)$$

288 In summary, the reaction network finally proposed for establishing the global kinetic
 289 model and parameter estimation is composed of seven reactions as described in Table 1.

290 **TABLE 1**

291 *3.4. The ordinary differential equation system*

292 Considering isothermal fixed bed reactor, with ideal plug flow model, the differential
 293 material balance for the species i is expressed as

$$294 \quad \frac{dC_i}{d(W/Q)} = \sum_{j=I}^{VII} n_{i,j} r_j \quad (16)$$

295 where r_j represents the rate of reaction I to VII (Table 1) and $n_{i,j}$ are the stoichiometric
 296 coefficients of component i in reaction j , considered positive for formed species and
 297 negative for disappeared species. Thus, the reaction rate for each component in the
 298 medium is evaluated as:

$$299 \quad \frac{dC_{NH_3}}{d[W/Q]} = -r_I - r_{III} - 2r_{IV} - 4r_V - 3r_{VI} \quad (17)$$

$$300 \quad \frac{dC_{NO}}{d[W/Q]} = -r_{II} - r_{III} - r_{IV} \quad (18)$$

$$301 \quad \frac{dC_{NO_2}}{d[W/Q]} = r_{II} - r_{IV} - 3r_V - 4r_{VI} \quad (19)$$

$$302 \quad \frac{dC_{N_2O}}{d[W/Q]} = \frac{7}{2}r_{VI} - 2r_{VII} \quad (20)$$

303

304 **4. Results and discussion**

305 *4.1. Design of experiments*

306 As above mentioned, first step for planning kinetic experiments was to consider the
 307 possibility of monitoring a limited number of components by choosing a subset of
 308 reactions of those included in the whole reaction network in Table 1. This reduced
 309 subset consisted of reactions V, VI and VII corresponding to the NO₂ SCR reaction and
 310 formation-decomposition of N₂O, in the absence of NO and oxygen in the feed stream.

311 In this sense, 62 experiments were designed at the conditions established in sets 1 and 2
 312 (Table 2), feeding NO₂ and NH₃ with initial concentration ratios $C_{\text{NO}_2}^0 / C_{\text{NH}_3}^0 = 300/300$
 313 ppm (29 experiments) and $C_{\text{NO}_2}^0 / C_{\text{NH}_3}^0 = 300/400$ ppm (33 experiments), and
 314 temperature of 225, 250, 300 and 350 °C. The composition of the outlet stream for each
 315 experiment is detailed in Tables S1 and S2 (supplementary material), respectively.

316 TABLE 2

317 It was not possible to propose another subset of reactions whose analysis could be done
 318 independently, since the introduction of NO in the feed stream starts up all the reactions
 319 in the whole network (reactions I to VII) and all products formed in the environment.
 320 Then, 36 experiments (set 3, from 63 to 98) were performed for the standard SCR
 321 reaction (NO+NH₃+O₂), with $C_{\text{NO}}^0 / C_{\text{NH}_3}^0 = 300/800$ and $800/300$ ppm, $C_{\text{O}_2}^0 = 6\%$, and
 322 $T = 225, 250, 300$ and 350 °C; 22 experiments (set 4, from 99 to 120) for ammonia
 323 oxidation, with $C_{\text{NH}_3}^0 = 300\text{-}5000$ ppm and $C_{\text{O}_2}^0 = 6\%$, $T = 225, 250$ and 300 °C; 13
 324 experiments (set 5, from 121 to 133) for NO oxidation, with $C_{\text{NO}}^0 = 200, 330$ ppm and
 325 $C_{\text{O}_2}^0 = 6\%$ between 150 and 500 °C; and 43 experiments (set 6, from 134 to 176) for fast
 326 SCR reaction (NO+NO₂+NH₃), with $C_{\text{NO}}^0 / C_{\text{NO}_2}^0 / C_{\text{NH}_3}^0 = 300/300/300, 300/300/600$ and
 327 $300/300/900$ ppm, and $T = 225, 250$ and 300 °C. The volume of catalyst in the reactor
 328 was diluted with inert quartz until 2 ml in all experiments. The weight of the catalyst
 329 and the feed stream flowrate as well as the outlet composition obtained for all
 330 experiment are detailed in Tables S3, S4, S5 and S6 (supplementary material),
 331 respectively.

332 4.2. Estimation of kinetic parameters

333 4.2.1. First approach for N₂O formation-decomposition reactions

334 As explained in design of experiments, the kinetic data obtained from experiments 1 to
 335 62 (sets 1 and 2) were analyzed independently, with the NO₂, NH₃ and N₂O species
 336 monitored during reactions V, VI and VII, as reported in Table 1. For this subsystem
 337 with only three reactions in the network, the following differential ordinary equations
 338 have to be solved:

$$339 \frac{dC_{\text{NH}_3}}{d[W/Q]} = -4r_{\text{V}} - 3r_{\text{VI}} \quad (21)$$

340
$$\frac{dC_{\text{NO}_2}}{d[W/Q]} = -3r_{\text{V}} - 4r_{\text{VI}} \quad (22)$$

341
$$\frac{dC_{\text{N}_2\text{O}}}{d[W/Q]} = \frac{7}{2}r_{\text{VI}} - 2r_{\text{VII}} \quad (20)$$

342 The kinetic constants were expressed as a function of temperature according to the
 343 Arrhenius's expression, in the following reparametrized form, which improves stability
 344 in the computational program,

345
$$k_j = k_{j,523} \cdot \exp\left(\frac{E_j}{R} \left(\frac{1}{523} - \frac{1}{T}\right)\right) \quad (23)$$

346 Similarly, the ammonia equilibrium constant with temperature is expressed as

347
$$K_{\text{NH}_3} = K_{\text{NH}_3,523} \cdot \exp\left(\frac{-\Delta H_j}{R} \left(\frac{1}{523} - \frac{1}{T}\right)\right) \quad (24)$$

348 To find the optimal parameters the following sum of squares of deviations between
 349 experimental and calculated values of concentration for each component has to be
 350 minimized, i.e.

351
$$\min \sum_{\forall i}^{\text{no. exp.}} (C_{i,\text{exp}} - C_{i,\text{calc}})^2 \rightarrow \text{optimal parameters} \quad (25)$$

352 The parameter estimation program was implemented in MATLAB R2014b. For the
 353 optimization procedure, different algorithms have been tested, resulting the Nelder-
 354 Meat algorithm that provided higher stability. Once initial conditions and parameter
 355 values defined, the optimization subroutine was launched for searching the optimal
 356 parameters by solving the ordinary differential equations (21), (22) and (20); hence, the
 357 output NH₃, NO₂ and N₂O concentrations are calculated and the objective equation (25)
 358 evaluated until minimization. The optimal values of the resulting kinetic parameters are
 359 shown in Table 3.

360

TABLE 3

361 Figure 1 shows the output NH₃, NO₂ and N₂O concentration versus space time, both
 362 experimental (points) and calculated (lines). Graphs on the left correspond to
 363 experiments with NH₃/NO₂ equimolar concentration in the feed stream, 300/300 ppm, at
 364 temperature of 225, 250 and 300 °C. The good quality of fitting between data simulated

365 by the reduced kinetic model and experimental data observed in Figure 1, validates
366 assumptions made previously by substitution of reaction (8) by reaction (14), and
367 inclusion of C_{NO_2} in the kinetic equation (15), corresponding to reactions VI and VII
368 (Table 1), respectively.

369

FIGURE 1

370 Similarly, graphs on right side of Figure 1 show the output NH_3 , NO_2 and N_2O
371 concentration vs. space time for $C_{\text{NO}_2}^0 / C_{\text{NH}_3}^0 = 300/400$ ppm, at temperature of 225, 250
372 and 300 °C. A good fitting between calculated and experimental data can be seen for all
373 experiments in Figure 1, for both ratios, especially at the intermediate temperature of
374 250 °C. A parallel evolution is observed between NH_3 and NO_2 consumption and
375 formation of N_2O , whose concentration is practically maintained constant at high space
376 time. This suggests that N_2O is formed by reaction between NO_2 and NH_3 , and that N_2O
377 decomposition is apparently negligible at these conditions. Also, curves of N_2O
378 formation seems not to be dependent of the reactant ratio in the feed stream, so that NO_2
379 consumption appears as the rate-controlling step of the reaction sub-network formed by
380 reactions V, VI and VII.

381 Some disagreement between calculated and experimental data is observed at 300 °C, for
382 space time in the range 0.5-1 (g cat.) h m^{-3} , giving underestimated calculated values of
383 NO_2 and NH_3 , as NO_2 is rapidly consumed for experiments with low space time. In case
384 internal diffusional resistances in the catalyst could be the cause of this deviation, this
385 internal mass transfer limitation will be estimated afterwards.

386 4.2.2. Kinetic parameters for the whole reaction network

387 Sets 3, 4, 5 and 6 of experiments in Table 2 enter NO and/or O_2 as reactant, this making
388 all reactions in the network to be running simultaneously. Thus, to estimate the kinetic
389 parameters of the whole system (7 reactions in Table 1), all 176 experimental data in the
390 design (Tables S1 to S6, supplementary material) should be treated in the statistical
391 analysis.

392 Parameter estimation was made using same methodology as defined in the previous
393 paragraph, but considering the ordinary differential equation system composed of
394 equations (17) to (20), in which the evolution of NH_3 , NO , NO_2 , and N_2O
395 concentrations is mathematically described, and maintaining equation (25) as the

396 objective function to be minimized. Kinetic parameters previously estimated for
397 reactions V, VI and VII, were used as initial values in this second step. Table 4 shows
398 the obtained optimal estimated parameters (preexponential factors and activation
399 energies) for each reaction included in the NO_x NH₃-SCR system. Also the confidence
400 intervals for a 95% probability of the activation energies are shown. It can be found a
401 great similarity of estimated activation energies for reactions V, VI and VII, with those
402 estimated previously (Table 3) when the subsystem considering only these three
403 reactions was analyzed. However, difference of some order of magnitude is observed in
404 the preexponential factors as a consequence of including new reaction rate terms in
405 equations (17) and (19) relative to equations (21) and (22).

406

TABLE 4

407 The comparison of the obtained activation energy values with those reported in
408 literature by other authors reveals a good agreement, especially for reactions III, IV and
409 V. For the standard SCR, the activation energy in this work resulted in 91.5 kJ mol⁻¹,
410 similar to 89.1 obtained by Metkar et al. [10] for Cu/CHA, and 84.9 kJ mol⁻¹ by Olsson
411 et al. [36] for Cu/ZSM-5. For fast SCR, the value of 42.0 kJ mol⁻¹ resulted close but
412 lower, compared with 77.1 kJ mol⁻¹ [10] and 85.1 kJ mol⁻¹ [36]. Finally, for NO₂ SCR
413 reaction an activation energy value of 118.1 kJ mol⁻¹ was obtained, intermediate
414 between 136.3 and 72.3 kJ mol⁻¹ reported by Metkar et al. [10] and Olsson et al. [36],
415 respectively.

416 There are not so many experimental runs under same operational conditions to draw
417 concentration vs. space time curves, as the design of experiments was built with the aim
418 of covering the most extended range of different variables. As an example, Figure 2
419 shows, for $T = 250$ °C, the outlet NO concentration curve calculated with the estimated
420 parameters of the model and disposable experimental data in the standard SCR reaction
421 for NO/NH₃ concentration ratios of 800/300, 300/300 and 300/800 ppm. Good fitting
422 between experimental and calculated concentrations is observed for this set of
423 experiments.

424

FIGURE 2

425 In order to verify the quality of fitting for the whole experimental design, the outlet NO
426 concentration calculated with optimal estimated parameters vs. experimental data are
427 represented in Figure 3, including standard SCR (experiments 63-98, Table S3), NO

428 oxidation (experiments 121-133, Table S5) and fast SCR reaction (experiments 134-
429 176, Table S6), achieved at all temperatures. An auxiliary diagonal has been drawn to
430 facilitate the evaluation of deviations, and different symbols (and colors in the
431 electronic version) for each series of experiments corresponding to different reactions.

432 **FIGURE 3**

433 Similarly, Figure 4 shows deviations between experimental outlet NH_3 concentrations
434 and calculated with the optimal estimated parameters, including $\text{NO}_2 + \text{NH}_3$ reactions
435 (experiments 1-62, Tables S1 and S2), standard SCR reaction (experiments 63-98,
436 Table S3), NH_3 oxidation (experiments 99-120, Table S4), and fast SCR reaction
437 (experiments 134-176, Table S6), for all studied temperatures. Again, a good correlation
438 between experimental and calculated data can be observed for all studied reactions. A
439 slightly higher deviation is observed for data corresponding to NH_3 oxidation (red
440 asterisk symbol), although these experiments were achieved with ammonia initial
441 concentration until 5000 ppm, much higher than that needed for this component in the
442 real diesel automobile application.

443 **FIGURE 4**

444 Figure 5 shows calculated vs. experimental outlet NO_2 concentrations for 141
445 experiments, including the initial subsystem composed of reactions V, VI and VII
446 (experiments 1-62, Tables S1 and S2), standard SCR reaction where NO_2 is formed
447 (experiments 63-98, Table S3), and fast SCR reaction. In this case, an important
448 deviation is observed for the fast SCR reaction at lower temperature (225 °C), where
449 estimated concentration is overestimated, apparently with lower NO_2 disappearance
450 than experimental values.

451 **FIGURE 5**

452 Also the N_2O formation is analyzed in Figure 6, which represents the correlation
453 between estimated and experimental outlet N_2O concentrations for $\text{NO} + \text{NH}_3$ reactions
454 (experiments 1-62, Tables S1 and S2), NO oxidation (experiments 121-133, Table S5),
455 and fast SCR reaction (experiments 134-176, Table S6) for the studied range of
456 temperature. No so good regression as for previous components is observed for this
457 undesired subproduct of the NO_x NH_3 -SCR system. This component was never fed in
458 any of the experimental runs. One must take into account the narrower range of
459 variation of N_2O (70 ppm), in comparison to the other components, namely NO , NH_3

460 and NO₂, included in the feed stream with at least 300 ppm. Another reason of the lack
 461 of fitting can be consequence of mathematical restrictions in the regression procedure,
 462 which is considering same ponderation for all compounds when the objective function
 463 is evaluated. Compounds in higher concentration contribute more importantly in the
 464 optimization process, which tries to find best fitting for concentration of these
 465 compounds, specifically NO and NH₃.

466 **FIGURE 6**

467 In order to assess the quality of the regression, an analysis of variance was performed.
 468 Table 5 shows the most representative values of the analysis. The model is able to
 469 explain a large percentage of the variation sources with a determination coefficient of r^2
 470 = 0.952. The F test results in a value much higher than that tabulated for a 99%
 471 probability (F=2.3), so the proposed model for the NO_x NH₃-SCR system is consistent,
 472 and explains with good statistical significance the evolution of NO, NH₃, NO₂ and N₂O
 473 concentrations for the large number of experiments realized. The standard error
 474 calculated resulted in 1.3×10^{-3} mol m⁻³, which is equivalent to 29 ppm.

475 **TABLE 5**

476 *4.3. Influence of mass transfer inside the catalyst particle*

477 The GHSV=90,000 h⁻¹ used in experimental runs corresponds to a linear velocity of
 478 gases through the catalyst bed of 37 cm s⁻¹, which apparently assure the absence of mass
 479 transfer control around the catalyst particle [70, 71]. However, due to high reaction rate
 480 under some reaction conditions, the mass transport inside the pores of the catalyst
 481 should be checked by determination of the Thiele modulus,

$$482 \quad \phi = \frac{V_p}{S_p} \sqrt{\frac{r_i}{C_{A,s}} \frac{1}{D_{eff}}} \quad (26)$$

483 and the effectiveness factor,

$$484 \quad \eta = \frac{3}{\phi} \left[\frac{1}{\tanh \phi} - \frac{1}{\phi} \right] \quad (27)$$

485 The maximum reaction rate value was determined for each of the seven considered
 486 reactions under the most unfavorable conditions. Table 6 shows the values of the Thiele
 487 modulus and effectiveness factor determined by equations (26) and (27), respectively.
 488 Our kinetic model predicts the highest reaction rates for reactions II (NO oxidation) and

489 III (standard SCR), for which effectiveness factors of 0.961 and 0.960 are determined at
490 300 °C. For the remaining reactions, the estimated effectiveness factor resulted in values
491 higher than 0.998. Therefore, with effectiveness factors greater than 0.96, the internal
492 diffusion control can be considered negligible up to 300 °C.

493 At 350 °C, the reaction rate of the standard SCR reaction increases notably, resulting in
494 an estimated effectiveness factor of 0.844. At these conditions, the concentration
495 gradients inside the catalyst particle begins to be appreciable, at least at the reactor inlet
496 where reaction rate is maximum; however, when reactant concentration is decreasing
497 along the reactor intraparticle gradients are progressively decreasing to negligible
498 values, even at 350 °C. The estimated effectiveness factor resulted in values above 0.95
499 for all reactions in the proposed kinetic model, validating the assumption of negligible
500 intraparticle diffusional control, practically under all experimental conditions managed
501 in this work for kinetic parameter estimation.

502 **TABLE 6**

503

504 **5. Conclusions**

505 A steady-state global kinetic model for the NO_x NH₃-SCR reaction system in excess of
506 oxygen has been proposed. The overall kinetic model consists of the following
507 reactions: (I) NH₃ oxidation, (II) NO oxidation, (III) standard SCR reaction, (IV) fast
508 SCR reaction, (V) NO₂ SCR reaction, (VI) N₂O formation and (VII) N₂O
509 decomposition. The proposed kinetic scheme postulates a Langmuir-Hinshelwood
510 formalism between adsorbed ammonia and weakly adsorbed NO species, which
511 simplifies to Rideal-Eley reaction rate equations with only ammonia adsorbed and NO
512 reacting directly from the gas phase.

513 An initial set of 62 experiments were designed, with only NO₂ and NH₃ in the feed
514 stream that allowed to get a first estimation of kinetic parameters of reactions V, VI and
515 VII, and considering nearly inexistence of reactions I to IV because of the absence NO
516 and O₂ in the feed stream. The parameter estimation mathematical program was
517 implemented in Matlab R2014b, and minimization —by the Nelder-Mead algorithm—
518 of the sum of squares of deviation between experimental and calculated NO, NH₃, NO₂,
519 N₂O concentrations was derived by solution of the material balance ordinary differential
520 equation system. The proposed model resulted in a good agreement between calculated

521 and experimental NH_3 and NO_2 concentrations at the outlet, for initial concentrations of
522 300/300 and 400/300 ppm, temperatures of 225, 250 and 300 °C, and space times (W/Q)
523 up to 8 (g cat.) h m⁻³. This range pretends to cover operational conditions simulating the
524 real application for NO_x removal of diesel and lean mixture engines aftertreatment
525 systems.

526 The introduction of NO activates all the seven reactions of the proposed global NO_x
527 NH_3 -SCR system. Additional extensive experimentation was designed up to a total of
528 176 experiments, including NO oxidation, NH_3 oxidation, standard SCR reaction and
529 fast SCR reaction. Same mathematical procedure as before was used for finding the
530 optimal estimated parameters, namely activation energy and frequency factors, for each
531 reaction in the model, including adsorption energy of ammonia. The optimal activation
532 energies resulted in 91.5, 42.0, and 118 kJ mol⁻¹, for the standard, fast and NO_2 SCR
533 reactions, respectively.

534 The determination coefficient of the proposed global kinetic model resulted in 0.952
535 with great statistical significance, with the F test calculated for a probability of 99%
536 more than a hundred times that statistically tabulated. The outlet concentrations of
537 major reactants in the NO_x NH_3 -SCR system —NO, NH_3 and NO_2 — result accurately
538 estimated by the model, with the exception of an overestimated NO_2 concentration for
539 the fast SCR reaction at the lower temperature of 225 °C (good for higher temperatures).

540 Some limitation has been found in the optimal estimation of the undesired N_2O
541 subproduct in the NO_x NH_3 -SCR system, due to low formation levels under the studied
542 conditions, which apparently reduces the weight of these experimental data in the global
543 parameter estimation procedure. Also, experimental error for so low concentrations can
544 be expected to be higher. In any case, the model is able to fit relatively well an
545 important number of experiments.

546 We are nowadays including the global model proposed in this paper, in new computer
547 programs to simulate the behavior of the NO_x NH_3 -SCR system in real aftertreatment
548 catalytic converters in the form of washcoated monoliths under one- or
549 multidimensional reactor models, where diffusional resistances and different flow
550 behavior need to be considered. This, which will be the aim of a following paper, will
551 allow predicting the catalyst performance in terms of the washcoat characteristics as
552 well as operational variables, especially temperature window performance.

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558

559 **Nomenclature**

560	$C_{i, \text{exp}}$	Concentration of i species experimentally determined, mol m ⁻³ .
561	$C_{i, \text{calc}}$	Concentration of i species calculated in the kinetic model, mol m ⁻³ .
562	$C_{i, s}$	Concentration of i species in the surface, mol m ⁻³ .
563	$D_{i, \text{eff}}$	Effective diffusion of I element in gaseous mixture, m ² s ⁻¹ .
564	E_j	Activation energy of reaction j, kJ mol ⁻¹ .
565	k_j	Kinetic rate constants of reaction j, units in Table 4
566	k_j^0	Pre-exponential coefficient in Arrhenius equation of reaction j, units of k_j .
567	K_{NH_3}	Equilibrium constant of NH ₃ adsorption-desorption, m ³ mol ⁻¹ .
568	$K_{\text{NO}}^{\text{eq}}$	Equilibrium constant of NO oxidation reaction, m ^{1.5} mol ^{-0.5} .
569	$n_{i,j}$	Stoichiometric coefficient of element i in reaction j.
570	Q	Flow rate, m ³ s ⁻¹ .
571	R	Ideal gas constant, 8,314 J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹ .
572	r_j	Rate of reaction j, mol g ⁻¹ h ⁻¹ .
573	S_p	Pore surface, m ² .
574	T	Temperature, °C.
575	V_p	Total pore volume, cm ³ g ⁻¹ .
576	W	Catalyst weight, g.
577	W/Q	Space time, (g cat.) h m ⁻³ .

578 *Greek symbols*

579	ΔH_j	Heat of reaction j, kJ mol ⁻¹ .
580	$\theta_{\text{NH}_3}^j$	Surface coverage of adsorbed NH ₃ at site j.
581	ϕ	Thiele module
582	η	Effectiveness factor

583

584

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706 **Table and Figure captions**

707

708 Table 1. SCR reaction network and kinetic expressions.

709 Table 2. Design of experiments, total = 176 experiments, distributed into six categories
710 according to different compounds in feed stream for analyzing different
711 reactions included in the SCR network shown in Table 1.

712 Table 3. Optimal kinetic parameters estimated from nonlinear regression of
713 experimental data corresponding to reactions V, VI and VII (Table 1),
714 experiments 1-62 (Table 2).

715 Table 4. Optimal kinetic parameters from nonlinear regression of all experimental data
716 (176 experiments, Table 2) to the global kinetic model based on the seven
717 reactions proposed for the NO_x NH₃-SCR system (reactions I-VII, equations.
718 3.1-3.7).

719 Table 5. Analysis of variance for the regression of the proposed global kinetic model.

720 Table 6. Estimated values of the Thiele module and the effectiveness factor for each of
721 the stages of the globalized model, under the most unfavorable reaction
722 conditions in each case.

723

724 Figure 1. Experimental and calculated evolution of NH₃, NO₂ and N₂O concentration
725 with space time for the subsystem including reactions V, VI and VI. Left
726 side graphs: inlet NH₃/NO₂ concentration ratio, 300/300 ppm (experiments
727 1-29, Table S1). Right side graphs: inlet NH₃/NO₂ concentration ratio,
728 400/300 ppm (experiments 30-62, Table S2).

729 Figure 2. Experimental and calculated evolution of NO concentration with space time
730 in the standard SCR reaction for inlet NO/NH₃ concentration ratios of
731 800/300, 300/300 and 300/800 ppm (numbers on each point correspond to
732 experimental data in Table S3).

733 Figure 3. Outlet NO concentration calculated from the proposed global model vs.
734 experimental data obtained for NO oxidation (crosses, experiments 121-133,
735 Table S5), standard SCR reaction (solid triangles, experiments 63-98, Table

736 S3), and fast SCR reaction (empty squares, experiments 134-176, Table S6).
737 All studied temperatures are included.

738 Figure 4. Outlet NH_3 concentration calculated from the proposed global model vs.
739 experimental data obtained for $\text{NO}_2 + \text{NH}_3$ reactions (empty circles,
740 experiments 1-62, Tables S1 and S2), NH_3 oxidation (asterisk, experiments
741 99-120, Table S4), standard SCR reaction (solid triangles, experiments 63-
742 98, Table S3), and fast SCR reaction (empty squares, experiments 134-176,
743 Table S6). All studied temperatures are included.

744 Figure 5. Outlet NO_2 concentration calculated from the proposed global model vs.
745 experimental data obtained for $\text{NO}_2 + \text{NH}_3$ reactions (empty circles,
746 experiments 1-62, Tables S1 and S2), NO oxidation (crosses, experiments
747 121-133, Table S5), standard SCR reaction (solid triangles, experiments 63-
748 98, Table S3), and fast SCR reaction (empty squares, experiments 134-176,
749 Table S6). All studied temperatures are included.

750 Figure 6. Outlet N_2O concentration calculated from the proposed global model vs.
751 experimental data obtained for $\text{NO}_2 + \text{NH}_3$ reactions (empty circles,
752 experiments 1-62, Tables S1 and S2), NO oxidation (crosses, experiments
753 121-133, Table S5), and fast SCR reaction (empty squares, experiments
754 134-176, Table S6). All studied temperatures are included.

755

756

757

TABLE 1

Reaction	Kinetic equation
I. $\text{NH}_3 + 3/4 \text{O}_2 \rightarrow 1/2 \text{N}_2 + 3/2 \text{H}_2\text{O}$	$r_{\text{I}} = \frac{k_{\text{I}} C_{\text{NH}_3} C_{\text{O}_2}}{1 + K_{\text{NH}_3} C_{\text{NH}_3}}$
II. $\text{NO} + 1/2 \text{O}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{NO}_2$	$r_{\text{II}} = k_{\text{II}} (C_{\text{NO}} C_{\text{O}_2}^{0.5} - C_{\text{NO}_2} / K_{\text{NO}}^{\text{eq}})$
III. $\text{NH}_3 + \text{NO} + 1/4 \text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{N}_2 + 3/2 \text{H}_2\text{O}$	$r_{\text{III}} = \frac{k_{\text{III}} C_{\text{NH}_3} C_{\text{NO}} C_{\text{O}_2}}{1 + K_{\text{NH}_3} C_{\text{NH}_3}}$
IV. $2 \text{NH}_3 + \text{NO} + \text{NO}_2 \rightarrow 2 \text{N}_2 + 3 \text{H}_2\text{O}$	$r_{\text{IV}} = \frac{k_{\text{IV}} C_{\text{NH}_3} C_{\text{NO}} C_{\text{NO}_2}}{1 + K_{\text{NH}_3} C_{\text{NH}_3}}$
V. $4 \text{NH}_3 + 3 \text{NO}_2 \rightarrow 7/2 \text{N}_2 + 6 \text{H}_2\text{O}$	$r_{\text{V}} = \frac{k_{\text{V}} C_{\text{NH}_3} C_{\text{NO}_2}}{1 + K_{\text{NH}_3} C_{\text{NH}_3}}$
VI. $3 \text{NH}_3 + 4 \text{NO}_2 \rightarrow 7/2 \text{N}_2\text{O} + 9/2 \text{H}_2\text{O}$	$r_{\text{VI}} = \frac{k_{\text{VI}} C_{\text{NH}_3} C_{\text{NO}_2}}{1 + K_{\text{NH}_3} C_{\text{NH}_3}}$
VII. $2 \text{N}_2\text{O} \rightarrow 2 \text{N}_2 + \text{O}_2$	$r_{\text{VII}} = k_{\text{VII}} C_{\text{N}_2\text{O}} C_{\text{NO}_2}$

TABLE 2

Set	Reaction	W, g cat.	Q, l min ⁻¹	C _{NO} ⁰ , ppm	C _{NO₂} ⁰ , ppm	C _{NH₃} ⁰ , ppm	C _{O₂} ⁰ , %	T, °C	Experiments
1	NO ₂ +NH ₃	0.05-0.5	1-3.1	-	300	300	-	225-350	1 to 29
2	NO ₂ +NH ₃	0.05-0.5	1-3.1	-	300	400	-	225-350	30 to 62
3	NO+NH ₃ +O ₂	0.5	1-3.3	300, 800	-	300, 800	6	225-350	63 to 98
4	NH ₃ +O ₂	0.01-0.5	1-3.3	-	-	300-5000	6	225-300	99 to 120
5	NO+O ₂	0.5	1.56	200, 330	-	-	6	150-500	121 to 133
6	NO+NO ₂ +NH ₃	0.05-0.5	1-3.2	300	300	300, 600, 900	-	225-300	134 to 176

TABLE 3

Parameter	Activation energy, kJ mol ⁻¹	Preexponential factor	
		Value	Units
k_V	132.5	8.64×10^{15}	m ⁶ g ⁻¹ h ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
k_{VI}	145.0	3.77×10^{17}	m ⁶ g ⁻¹ h ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
k_{VII}	249.9	1.29×10^{27}	m ⁶ g ⁻¹ h ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
K_{NH_3}	99.23 ^a	7.57×10^{-7}	m ³ mol ⁻¹

^a In the case of NH₃ adsorption, this value corresponds to the adsorption process enthalpy (Eq. 24).

TABLE 4

Kinetic constant	Preexponential factor		Activation energy, kJ mol ⁻¹	Confidence interval (95%)
	Value	Units		
k_I	1.59×10^{12}	$\text{m}^6 \text{g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$	108.11	± 0.40
k_{II}	6.81×10^5	$\text{m}^{4.5} \text{m}^{-3} \text{h}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-0.5}$	12.39	± 3.01
k_{III}	1.09×10^{12}	$\text{m}^9 \text{g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-2}$	91.45	± 1.58
k_{IV}	9.40×10^9	$\text{m}^9 \text{g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-2}$	41.98	± 1.15
k_V	3.07×10^{12}	$\text{m}^6 \text{g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$	118.10	± 29.21
k_{VI}	4.48×10^{18}	$\text{m}^6 \text{g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$	152.34	± 1.44
k_{VII}	2.45×10^{28}	$\text{m}^6 \text{g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$	257.92	± 6.16
K_{NH_3}	7.66×10^{-7}	$\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$	99.19 ^a	-
$K_{\text{NO}}^{\text{eq.}}$	8.61×10^{-4}	$\text{m}^{1.5} \text{mol}^{-0.5}$	57.28 ^a	-

^a In the case of NH₃ and NO, this values correspond to the enthalpies of the adsorption process and the oxidation reaction, respectively.

TABLE 5

Error source	Sum squares	Freedom degrees	Mean square	F	Probability
Regression	5.58×10^{-3}	14	3.98×10^{-4}	226.1	>99.9%
Residual	2.84×10^{-4}	161	1.76×10^{-6}		
Total	5.86×10^{-3}	175			

TABLE 6

Reaction	$T = 300\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$		$T = 350\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$	
	Thiele	Effectiveness	Thiele	Effectiveness
	module	factor	module	factor
	(ϕ)	(η)	(ϕ)	(η)
$\text{NH}_3 + 3/4\text{O}_2 \rightarrow 1/2\text{N}_2 + 3/2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	0.14	0.999	0.34	0.992
$\text{NO} + 1/2\text{O}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{NO}_2$	0.78	0.961	0.87	0.953
$\text{NH}_3 + \text{NO} + 1/4\text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{N}_2 + 3/2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	0.80	0.960	1.73	0.844
$2\text{NH}_3 + \text{NO} + \text{NO}_2 \rightarrow 2\text{N}_2 + 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	0.12	0.999	0.18	0.998
$4\text{NH}_3 + 3\text{NO}_2 \rightarrow 7/2\text{N}_2 + 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	0.005	1.000	0.014	1.000
$3\text{NH}_3 + 4\text{NO}_2 \rightarrow 7/2\text{N}_2\text{O} + 9/2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	0.18	0.998	0.64	0.974
$2\text{N}_2\text{O} \rightarrow 2\text{N}_2 + \text{O}_2$	0.10	0.999	0.84	0.956

Figure 1
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Supplementary Material

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